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Subformula Linking for Separation Logic with Forward and Backward Linking

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Abstract

Proof by pointing and the extension subformula linking are interactive proof methods which allow reducing propositions based on mouse-interactions. We present a system which allows subformula linking in separation logic, which is a substructural logic that argues about memory.

Our system implements a recent advancement for linking under quantifiers by Mulder and Krebbers called Quantifying the Uninstantiated (QU), which reduces backtracking and prevents unwanted links compared to previous iterations. Our system is the first system to use QU while also allowing linking propositions at arbitrary depth for both hypothesis-hypothesis and hypothesis-goal links.

Additionally, we also describe an implementation in Rocq in the form of our `link` tactic. The resulting system provides an intuitive alternative that can be used largely by itself, or in conjunction with Iris Proof Mode.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

To reason effectively about increasingly complex programs that manage memory, Bunched Implication logic [O’Hearn and Pym, 1999] and separation logic [O’Hearn et al., 2001] have emerged as a particularly successful tools. For example, they have been used to verify safe encapsulation of unsafe Rust code with the RustBelt [Jung et al., 2018] project and are used as the foundations of the Verified Software Toolchain [Cao et al., 2018], which is a combination of tools that allow Hoare-based verification of C programs and are built on top of CompCert [Leroy, 2009], a verified C compiler.

The core idea of separation logic is local reasoning using the connectives for *separating conjunction* ($*$) and separating implication or (magic) *wand* ($-*$), which allow reasoning about disjoint portions of memory, enabling a proof to focus only on the portion of memory that a piece of code actually accesses. Separation logic is substructural, disallowing some resources to be used multiple times, and requiring those resources to be used at least once for linear separation logics. A fundamental pattern in separation logic proofs involves matching resources on both sides of an implication. For instance, to prove a proposition $P * Q \multimap Q * P$, one intuitively ”connects” the resources P being consumed at the left-hand side of the wand with the resource P being produced at the right-hand side of the wand and does so similarly for the resources Q until no resources are unused or required.

The success of separation logic has spawned various tool assistants which specialize in either granular or full automation for proofs in separation logics. The main interactive proof assistant for separation logic is the Iris Proof Mode [Krebbers et al., 2017], which provides a powerful set of tactics and an embedded new goal state in Rocq. For (nearly) fully automatic proofs, there are systems that use SAT or SMT-like solvers to resolve Hoare triples of program specifications, like VeriFast [Jacobs et al., 2011], Viper [Müller et al., 2016] and Caper [Dinsdale-Young et al., 2017]. Additionally, there are systems based on logic programming [Kowalski, 1974] in existing general-purpose proof assistants like Rocq or Iris, such as Bedrock [Chlipala, 2013], Refined C [Sammler et al., 2021] and Diaframe [Mulder et al., 2022].

Separately, tools that use drag-and-drop as the main interaction method for proving propositions have been developed for various logics, which can create quick and intuitive proof construction steps. For example, we see *TAS* [Lüth and Wolff, 2000], a system for window inference logic build on top of Isabelle, the *Key prover* [Ahrendt and Grebing, 2016], an industry-focused prover for dynamic logic with a focus on the Java Modeling Language, and the very recent and still in development *Flower Prover* [Donato, 2024], which uses topological diagrams based on a calculus it calls *Flower Calculus* to represent and interact with the prove state.

The concept called *subformula linking* is a possible specifications for a drag-and-

drop systems. In subformula linking each drag-and-drop interaction ‘cancels’ or ‘links’ unifiable subformula. It can be applied to various logics such as first-order classical linear logic in the case of *Profound* [Chaudhuri, 2013], higher-order intuitionistic logic in the cases of *ProfInt* [Chaudhuri, 2021] and *Actema* [Donato et al., 2022], and even partial implementations of the idea for separation logic in the earlier mentioned Diaframe and Iris.

However, there does not exist a interactive subformula linking system designed for separation logic that allows users to interactively select and link subformulas at arbitrary depth. To illustrate what such a system could achieve, consider the following proposition:

$$P * (\exists x. P -* Q x) -* \exists y. Q y$$

We might want to connect either the propositions P with a single instruction, which could reduce the term to $(\exists x. Q x) -* \exists y. Q y$, or connect the propositions Q , which could reduce the term to $P -* \forall x. P$. The generated $\forall x.$ is a result of preserving the knowledge that the type is inhabited. There are some cases where such superfluous quantifiers are cleaned up, which we explain in Section 4.5.

This thesis aims to fill this gap by developing a logical system based on subformula linking in separation logic which allows a user to prove propositions by ‘linking’ subformulas at arbitrary depth and using both hypothesis-hypothesis and hypothesis-goal links. We implement this system in Rocq in such a way that it can be used in tandem with the standard Iris Proof Mode, so that the power of Iris can be used at the same time as the convenience of linking. We have not, however, created a graphical user interface with drag-and-drop interactions which uses this implementation, and leave it as future work Section 7.5.

1.1 Subformula Linking

The origins of proving propositions with point-and-click interactions are largely from the paper ‘Proof by pointing’ by Bertot et al. [1994]. It describes a process of progressing a sequent $\Gamma \vdash P$ based on selecting a single selected subformula. The interaction methods are based on various intuitionistic logics and provides an extension for classical logic. Depending on the location of the selected subformula, the goal is resolved or moved to a top-level proposition in the context or goal.

Next, the methods of proving formulas with mouse-based interactions moved on with a proposed extension from Proof By Pointing, which it called Point and Shoot, but is generally referred to as subformula linking. The first description of subformula linking started in first-order classical linear logic in the paper ‘Subformula Linking as an Interaction Method’ by Chaudhuri [2013]. The paper describes a calculus for linked structures, which allows the user to create a *link* by dragging a subformula to another subformula, with the intention of ‘cancelling’ these terms against each other if possible. It introduces a new connective which replaces the least common ancestor connective of the selected subformula. The result of this reduction depends on the location of the subformula. The paper also provides a prototype stand-alone implementation called *Profound*.

These ideas of subformula linking were developed further into an implementation called *ProfInt* by Chaudhuri [2021], which is a first-order intuitionistic version of the Profound system. The proofs generated by this proof assistant are capable of generating code for other proof assistants, such as Rocq, Isabelle and Lean. Although both theories of proving by linking are complete for their respective logics, the implementations do not implement some of the rules described by the system, so the implementations are not. The rules for quantifiers in this system do, however, occasionally reduce a tautology to a simplification that is equivalent to \perp , which results from a problem of scoping issues.

Building on the ideas of ProfInt, the *Actema* system by Donato et al. [2022] was developed as a more capable and user-friendly proof assistant for intuitionistic logic than ProfInt or similar systems. The system adds functionality such as copying propositions in a context, eliminating existential quantifiers and conjunctions in the context and introducing the conjunction in a goal $A \wedge B$ to create two goals. It also changes the rules for interacting with quantifiers. Unlike ProfInt, these rules do not have the same scoping issues and will therefore never produce these undesired simplifications.

There are, however, examples of propositions where a simplification is desired, but where Actema is incapable of finding it, which a recent paper called ‘Unification for Subformula Linking under Quantifiers’ by Mulder and Krebbers [2024] resolves. This paper addresses this limitation by changing the rules for quantifiers yet again by adding a rule which can add multiple quantifiers in a single application, which allows the system to resolve some scoping issues by what the paper calls *Quantifying the Uninstantiated* (QU). The paper describes a simple version of QU in first-order intuitionistic logic, but scales two implementations to higher-order separation logic, an expansion of the `iFrame` tactic from Iris Proof Mode [Krebbers et al., 2017] and as part of the main tactic `iStep` from Diaframe [Mulder et al., 2022], which is called repeatedly to fully automate proofs for Hoare triples of concurrent programs (see Section 6.2.2). The idea of subformula linking in both of these implementations is less important, however. Instead, these rules of QU are added to allow additional automatic simplification on top of the existing system. Neither of these implementations use the idea of proving by drag-and-drop interactions, and these implementations therefore do not allow forward reasoning by linking two subformula that are both in a hypothesis, for example.

1.2 Problem

Even though there are two implementations for separation logic, in Diaframe and Iris’ `iFrame`, that make use of the recent solution for dealing with quantifiers in subformula linking, neither of these are drag-and-drop based proof assistants that allow linking arbitrary subformula. More importantly, there is no implementation that uses QU and allows linking arbitrary subformula, which means there is no way to do forward reasoning with hypothesis-hypothesis links if the link requires ideas from QU. For example, we might want to link the proposition $G x y$ to $G (f z) y$ as a forward reasoning step in the following formula:

$$(\forall x. F x \multimap \exists y. G x y) * (\forall yz. G (f z) y \multimap P) \multimap P.$$

Neither implementations using QU provide this functionality, and Actema fails to find a link for this example when changing the wands to implications and separating conjunctions to standard conjunctions. Similarly, there exists no system that implements a way to link arbitrary subformulas for separation logic. All the implementations of QU are part of larger tactics, and therefore limit the scope to only top-level, hypothesis-goal links.

In a manual system, hypothesis-hypothesis links are desirable because they enable forward reasoning, which more closely resembles mathematical arguments in natural language. Additionally, hypothesis-hypothesis links were essential for completeness in earlier systems like ProfInt. While this and recent implementations focus on soundness rather than completeness in the sense that all propositions that are provable using the laws of the logic are also provable using just link interactions, the expressive power of these forward link is strictly increased by adding forward reasoning and is therefore closer to a complete system. Our system is not complete, however, which is considered future work Section 7.3.

1.3 Solution

In this thesis we describe a system which allows linking subformula in separation logic at arbitrary depth for both hypothesis-hypothesis and hypothesis-goal links. We use recent developments for reasoning under quantifiers [Mulder and Krebbers, 2024] and do so a limited subset of the substructural separation logic which uses only the $\multimap, *$ connectives and quantification. We also create an implementation in Rocq [Haaijman, 2025]. This tactic works in three steps, each implemented using Rocq type class system [Sozeau and Oury, 2008]. We start by splitting a context function from a kernel, where the top-level connective of the kernel is the least common ancestor connective of the propositions that are selected. This step enables linking at arbitrary depth. Next, we simplify the kernel using the ideas of subformula linking and QU, adding rules that use the idea of Quantifying the Uninstantiated for forward links. Finally, we do some cleanup, attempting to simplify the result as much as we can.

1.4 Contributions and Outline

In this thesis we describe our contributions in the following chapters:

2. In Chapter 2 we give some background for separation logic and the logic of bunched implication as a foundation for the rest of the paper
3. In Chapter 3 we describe the idea of our `link` tactic and how to use it.
4. In Chapter 4 we describe the theory of the system, which contains various judgments whose inference rules are set up to enable a sort of logical programming, where parts of the judgments are considered ‘input’ and other parts are considered ‘output’. Particularly, one of these judgments is capable of splitting a context function from a kernel, and two mutually recursive judgments that deal with linking under this context for either hypothesis-hypothesis links or hypothesis-goal links. For these judgments we also do an analysis of their non-determinism.
5. In Chapter 5 we give a short introduction into Rocq’s type class system and describe some of the challenges of implementing the judgments as type classes in Rocq. We focus on details we left out in the previous chapter such as quantification with dependent quantifiers.

The Rocq sources of these artifacts are in the supplementary material Haaijman [2025].

Chapter 2

Separation Logic

In Section 2.1 we will start by defining some of the basic connectives by describing entailments and some of the connectives of *Bunched Implication* (BI) logic. Then in Section 2.2 we will describe the main ideas of how to use BI logic through the simplest separation logic; a shallow implementation of heap predicates in a higher-order logic. Finally in Section 2.3 we will give the proof rules of our logic with some clarifications and highlights.

2.1 BI logic

The logic of Bunched Implications (BI) combines both ordinary intuitionistic connectives, like \wedge and \rightarrow which it calls additive, with the multiplicative connectives from linear logic \otimes and \multimap . Unlike ordinary intuitionistic logic, these connectives from linear logic do not allow using assumptions multiple times (Contraction) or adding irrelevant assumptions (Weakening).

BI describes a few ways of combining these ideas into a single logic. In this case, we consider our logic to be a pre-ordered set of $(Prop, \vdash)$ in a higher-order meta logic **Prop** such as Gallina from Rocq, together with the operations:

\mathbf{Emp}	$: Prop$	(‘empty resources’)
$\ulcorner _ \urcorner$	$: \mathbf{Prop} \rightarrow Prop$	(‘pure’ proposition)
$*$	$: Prop \times Prop \rightarrow Prop$	(‘separating conjunction’)
$-*$	$: Prop \times Prop \rightarrow Prop$	(‘separating implication’ or ‘magic wand’)
\forall, \exists	$: \forall \tau : \mathbf{Type}. (\tau \rightarrow Prop) \rightarrow Prop$	(Usual higher-order predicate connectives)
\top, \perp	$: Prop$	(Usual propositional connectives (1))
$\wedge, \vee, \rightarrow$	$: Prop \times Prop \rightarrow Prop$	(Usual propositional connectives (2))

We will use the shorthand $\vdash P$ for $\mathbf{Emp} \vdash P$ and $P \dashv\vdash Q$ for to mean both $P \vdash Q$ and $Q \vdash P$. The types $\tau : \mathbf{Type}$ can be any type from our meta logic, including type variables τ_i , function types and $Prop$ itself. There are many models for BI. each model can define their own set of basic atoms $\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{B}, \mathbb{C}$, etc, and specifications for the operations, but must follow the proof rules we present in Section 2.3. Before showing the rules themselves we present the standard heap model of Separation Logic, which is such a model for BI, to create some intuition for the proof rules.

2.2 The Standard Heap Model

We call a model for BI a *Separation Logic* when it argues about memory or resources. In this section we present the standard heap model from O’Hearn et al. [2001], without the stack. Unlike the original model, however, this example implementation is a shallow embedding in the logic of Rocq, Gallina, and considers propositions in separation logic to be *predicates on heaplets*, so an implementation of these separation propositions in Rocq would have the type $Prop \triangleq \text{heaplet} \rightarrow \mathbf{Prop}$

Ownership, in this example, describes locations and values stored on a *heaplet* that we have access to. We will model a heaplet h as a finite partial function from memory locations Loc (typically modelled as natural numbers) to values Val (also natural numbers for now), $h : Loc \rightarrow Val$. We will use the notation $h_1 \# h_2$ to indicate the domains of the heaplets h_1 and h_2 are disjoint, and use $h_1 \uplus h_2$ as the disjoint union of these heaplets (i.e. the union of functions with disjoint domain). Our only basic atom will be the ‘points-to’ operator \mapsto , described below.

The intuitive semantics and semantics in this implementation of the new connectives are the following:

- **Points-to** ($l \mapsto v$): The basic atom proposition $l \mapsto v$ describes that the heaplet h that we own consists of *exactly one* allocated memory ‘cell’ such that the value v is stored at location l . In our implementation this becomes the function that maps heaps to the singleton heap containing exactly this mapping:

$$l \mapsto v \triangleq \lambda h. h = \{l := v\}$$

- **Empty heap** (**Emp**): The proposition **Emp** says that the part of the heaplet we own h is empty. Since our resources are heaps in this model, we call it the *empty heap*. In our implementation, it requires the domain of h to be the empty set:

$$\mathbf{Emp} \triangleq \lambda h. \text{dom}(h) = \emptyset$$

- **Pure propositions** ($\ulcorner _ \urcorner$): The proposition $\ulcorner \mathbf{P} \urcorner$ holds if the proposition \mathbf{P} holds in the meta-logic, without any resources. The implementation becomes:

$$\ulcorner \mathbf{P} \urcorner \triangleq \lambda h. \mathbf{P} \wedge \text{dom}(h) = \emptyset$$

- **Separating Conjunction** ($*$): The proposition $P * Q$ describes that the heaplet we own can be split into two disjoint parts h_1 and h_2 such that h_1 satisfies proposition P and h_2 satisfies Q . In the implementation, this becomes:

$$P * Q \triangleq \lambda h. \exists h_1 h_2. h = h_1 \uplus h_2 \wedge P h_1 \wedge Q h_2$$

- **Magic Wand** ($-*$): The proposition $P -* Q$ holds for our current heaplet h if, for any possible heaplet h' that is disjoint from h and satisfies assertion P , the combined heap $h \cup h'$ would satisfy assertion Q . In other words, the proposition says that Q holds, once we are given ownership of P . In the implementation this becomes:

$$P -* Q \triangleq \lambda h. \forall h'. (h' \# h) \rightarrow P h' \rightarrow Q (h' \uplus h)$$

- **Entailment** (\vdash): The statement $P \vdash Q$ is not a statement in $Prop$, but a statement in our meta logic \mathbf{Prop} , and says that for all heaplets where P holds, so does Q . The example implementation becomes

$$P \vdash Q \triangleq \forall h. P h \rightarrow Q h$$

Laws of Standard Intuitionistic Logic (Additive)

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\rightarrow\)-INTRO} \\
\frac{P \wedge Q \vdash R}{P \vdash Q \rightarrow R}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\rightarrow\)-ELIM} \\
\frac{P \vdash Q \rightarrow R}{P \wedge Q \vdash R}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\wedge\)-INTRO} \\
\frac{P \vdash Q \quad P \vdash R}{P \vdash Q \wedge R}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\wedge\)-ELIM} \\
P \wedge Q \vdash P
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\top\)-INTRO} \\
P \vdash \top
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\perp\)-ELIM} \\
\perp \vdash P
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\vee\)-INTRO} \\
P \vdash P \vee Q
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\vee\)-ELIM} \\
\frac{P \vdash R \quad Q \vdash R}{P \vee Q \vdash R}
\end{array}$$

Laws of Quantifiers

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\forall\)-INTRO} \\
\frac{\forall x. P \vdash Q}{P \vdash \forall x. Q}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\forall\)-ELIM} \\
\frac{P \vdash \forall x. Q}{P \vdash Q[x := t]}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\exists\)-INTRO} \\
\frac{P \vdash Q[x := t]}{P \vdash \exists x. Q}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(\exists\)-ELIM} \\
\frac{\forall x. Q \vdash R}{\exists x. Q \vdash R}
\end{array}$$

Laws of Bunched Implications (Multiplicative)

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(*\)-INTRO} \\
\frac{P * Q \vdash R}{P \vdash Q * R}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(*\)-ELIM} \\
\frac{P \vdash Q * R}{P * Q \vdash R}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(*\)-MONO} \\
\frac{P_1 \vdash Q_1 \quad P_2 \vdash Q_2}{P_1 * P_2 \vdash Q_1 * Q_2}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(*\)-EMP} \\
P * \text{Emp} \dashv\vdash P
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(*\)-COMM} \\
Q * P \dashv\vdash P * Q
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{\(*\)-ASSOC} \\
P * (Q * R) \dashv\vdash (P * Q) * R
\end{array}$$

Figure 2.1: Laws of the logic of Bunched Implication.

The semantics of the well-known connectives from predicate and propositional logic are mostly equivalent to their counterparts, but lifted to separation logic:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\top \triangleq \lambda h. \mathbf{True} & \perp \triangleq \lambda h. \mathbf{False} \\
(P \rightarrow Q) \triangleq \lambda h. P h \rightarrow Q h & (P \wedge Q) \triangleq \lambda h. P h \wedge Q h \\
(\forall x : \tau. P) \triangleq \lambda h. \forall x : \tau. P h & (\exists x : \tau. P) \triangleq \lambda h. \exists x : \tau. P h \\
(P \vee Q) \triangleq \lambda h. P h \vee Q h &
\end{array}$$

We are overloading some notation in these definitions. The left-hand side is notation for the proposition in Separation logic, which we define in the meta-logic on the right-hand side.

Using these connectives we can now make concise statements about memory, such as $l_1 \mapsto v_1 * l_2 \mapsto v_2$, which means that we own *exactly* two cells in the heaplet: the cell at location l_1 with value v_1 and the cell at location l_2 with value v_2 . If we append $*\top$ to this proposition to get $l_1 \mapsto v_1 * l_2 \mapsto v_2 * \top$, we get heaplets that contain *at least* these cells, all other possible heaps that are disjoint from these two are contained in the part of the heaplet where \top holds.

Some of the ordinary propositional connectives become much less useful when arguing about memory. For example, the proposition $l_1 \mapsto v_1 \wedge l_2 \mapsto v_2$ implies that $l_1 = l_2$ and $v_1 = v_2$, because it says that a single heap h is both the singleton heap $\{l_1 := v_1\}$ and the singleton heap $\{l_2 := v_2\}$.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{P \vdash P * \text{Emp}} \text{*EMP} \quad \frac{}{Q \vdash Q} \text{\vdash-refl} \\
\hline
\frac{P * Q \vdash (P * \text{Emp}) * Q}{P * Q \vdash P * (\text{Emp} * Q)} \text{*MONO} \quad \frac{(P * \text{Emp}) * Q \vdash P * (\text{Emp} * Q)}{P * Q \vdash P * (\text{Emp} * Q)} \text{*ASSOC} \\
\hline
\text{\vdash-trans}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{P \vdash P} \text{\vdash-refl} \quad \frac{Q \vdash Q * \text{Emp}}{Q \vdash \text{Emp} * Q} \text{*EMP} \quad \frac{Q * \text{Emp} \vdash \text{Emp} * Q}{Q \vdash \text{Emp} * Q} \text{*COMM} \\
\hline
\frac{P * Q \vdash P * (\text{Emp} * Q)}{P * Q \vdash P * (\text{Emp} * Q)} \text{*MONO} \quad \text{\vdash-trans}
\end{array}$$

Figure 2.2: Two Derivations of $P * Q \vdash P * \text{Emp} * Q$ using the proof rules. Rules $\vdash\text{-refl}$ and $\vdash\text{-trans}$ are explicit uses of the reflexivity and transitivity of \vdash

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{F x * \text{Emp} \vdash F x}{F x * \text{Emp} \vdash F x} \text{*EMP} \quad \frac{\text{Emp} * F x \vdash F x * \text{Emp}}{\text{Emp} * F x \vdash F x} \text{*COMM} \\
\hline
\frac{\text{Emp} * F x \vdash F x}{\vdash F x * \text{Emp}} \text{\vdash-trans} \\
\hline
\frac{\vdash F x * \text{Emp}}{\vdash \exists y. F x * F y} \text{*INTRO} \\
\hline
\frac{\vdash \exists y. F x * F y}{\vdash \forall x. \exists y. F x * F y} \text{\forall-INTRO}
\end{array}$$

Figure 2.3: A derivation of $\vdash \forall x. \exists y. F x * F y$ using the proof rules

2.3 Proof Rules of BI and Separation Logic

The complete semantics of BI is given in Figure 2.1. The notation $\forall x.$ preceding a sequent with a larger gap is part of the meta-logic. Effectively, it implicitly adds appropriate side-conditions for the quantifiers. More precisely, $\forall x.$ it means that the sequent must hold soundly for arbitrary x . For example, in rule $\forall\text{-INTRO}$, the premise $\forall x. P \vdash Q$ means that the derivation of Q from P must be independent of x . Because the conclusion $\forall x. Q$ generalizes over x , x might be free in Q . However, since the derivation from P must hold for an arbitrary x , this requires that x cannot be free in P .

The additive section of the rules form the resource-insensitive fragment of the logic, and is based on standard intuitionistic rules. Note that for standard conjunction, the rule $\wedge\text{-INTRO}$ effectively duplicates the resources (Contraction), and rule $\wedge\text{-ELIM}$ shows a resource being discarded (Weakening).

The other additive rules are straightforward: $\rightarrow\text{-INTRO}$ discharges an assumption Q to introduce implication $Q \rightarrow R$, $\rightarrow\text{-ELIM}$ is a Modus Ponens that allows additional additive propositions in the context, $\top\text{-INTRO}$ says that \top is always derivable, $\perp\text{-ELIM}$ is Ex Falso, $\vee\text{-INTRO}$ introduces disjunction with an arbitrary proposition, and $\vee\text{-ELIM}$ performs case analysis on a disjunctive assumption.

Figure 2.3 shows an example of a derivation that uses some of the quantifier rules. The quantifier rules introduce and substitute higher-order variables.

The wand rules from BI, $\text{-*}\text{-INTRO}$ and $\text{-*}\text{-ELIM}$ match very closely to the implication rules of standard intuitionistic logic, $\rightarrow\text{-INTRO}$ and $\rightarrow\text{-ELIM}$, respectively. The other rules have no clear equivalent axiom. Rather, the intuitionistic equivalents of rules $\text{*}\text{-EMP}$, $\text{*}\text{-COMM}$ and $\text{*}\text{-ASSOC}$ for standard conjunction are all derivable. Much of the essential differences between the additive and multiplicate parts come from the lack of introduction and elimination rules for $*$. Instead, the most well-suited rule we know of for the idea of separation of resources is the monotonicity rule $\text{*}\text{-MONO}$.

Consider the derivations of $P * Q \vdash P * \text{Emp} * Q$ in Figure 2.2. In contrast to

intuitionistic logic, we can not simply duplicate the context $Q * P$ to prove both P and $(\text{Emp} * Q)$ separately. Instead, we order our resources so that we can *split* the resources in an appropriate way. We also need to use commutativity, associativity of $*$ and the transitivity of \vdash for even very simple examples. In general, finding how to split the resources is not straightforward.

The idea of *framing* simplifies the process of splitting the resources. Framing says that if we have a goal $R_1 * \dots * R_n \vdash P$, we should try to find a single index i and proposition Q such that $Q * R_i \vdash P$. After reordering and applying $*$ -MONO, we then eliminate this R_i immediately by reflexivity. After framing our new goal becomes $P' \vdash R_1 * \dots * R_{i-1} * R_{i+1} * R_n$, which is a simpler goal.

We see that these laws of BI hold in the standard heap model from Section 2.2. Firstly, the intuitionistic and quantifier laws all hold because of the lifting to the meta-logic, where the intuitionistic laws hold. The laws hold because of the following:

- $*$ -INTRO holds because the premise of the rule requires that any heap h that can be split into h_1 and h_2 with $P h_1$ and $Q h_2$ and $R (h_1 \uplus h_2)$, so if we only have $P h'_1$, it should follow that if we add $Q h'_2$ then $R (h_1 \uplus h_2)$, which is exactly what the arrow means.
- $*$ -ELIM holds with similar reasoning as $*$ -INTRO, but in the other direction.
- $*$ -MONO holds because we require that the heaplets are split in a disjoint way.
- $*$ -EMP holds because the disjoint union of the empty heaplet with another heaplet is exactly that other heaplet.
- $*$ -COMM and $*$ -ASSOC hold because the disjoint union operation is commutative and associative.

2.4 Derivations in BI and Iris Proof Mode

As we have seen in Figure 2.2, creating a derivation of a BI statement can be done as a proof tree using the rules from Figure 2.1 directly, but that is often quite tedious. This is especially so because it often requires many applications of the $*$ -ASSOC and $*$ -COMM rules and transitivity of \vdash . Instead, the Iris framework provides the *Iris Proof Mode* (IPM) from Krebbers et al. [2017].

The normal proof mode of Rocq shows a single context, which is a labeled list of assumptions that are implicitly connected with standard conjunctions. Because of this, items in this context can be duplicated or removed. IPM uses this context for the intuitionistic part of BI and for quantifiers and calls it the ‘pure’ context. Apart from that context, IPM also provides 2 additional contexts: the persistent context and the spatial context. The persistent context is for an extension on BI we will not discuss. The spatial context of IPM is for the multiplicative part of BI. This context is also a labeled list of propositions, but these propositions are implicitly connected with separating conjunctions instead of standard conjunctions. We can therefore neither duplicate nor throw away propositions in this spatial context.

Figure 2.4 Displays two derivations of the same proof term from Figure 2.2, $P * Q \vdash P * (\text{Emp} * Q)$. Anyone familiar with Rocq will see that IPM provides similar, but slightly different tactics from the standard Rocq tactics, like `intros` vs `iIntros`, `exact` vs `iExact`, etc. Since these tactics can use a different context, the arguments to many of these tactics have to be given as a string, but powerful ideas such as introduction patterns are present and even expanded upon.

There are additional differences to account for the differences in the logic, however. For example, there are multiple equivalents to the `split` tactic: `iSplitL` and `iSplitR`.

```

Lemma iris_demo (PROP: bi) (P Q : PROP) : P * Q ⊢ P * emp * Q.
Proof.
  (* P * Q ⊢ P * emp * Q *)
  iIntros "[HP HQ]".

  (* "HP" : P      *)
  (* "HQ" : Q      *)
  (* -----*    *)
  (* P * emp * Q *)
  iSplitL "HP"; [ | iSplitR ].

  (* "HP" : P      *)
  (* -----*    *)
  (* P              *)
  - iExact "HP".

  (* -----*    *)
  (* emp           *)
  - trivial.

  (* "HP" : Q      *)
  (* -----*    *)
  (* Q              *)
  - iAssumption.

  (* All goals completed. *)
Restart.
  iIntros "[HP HQ]".
  iFrame.
Qed.

```

Figure 2.4: Derivation of $P * Q \vdash P * (\text{Emp} * Q)$ using Iris Proof Mode

In contrast to standard intuitionistic logic, splitting the goal requires the resources to be split as well and these `iSplitL`, `iSplitR` move all the resources to the first and second goal by default respectively, or move specified resources to that goal if an additional argument with recourses is provided.

Finally, IPM provides tactics that are specialized for Separation Logic, such as the `iFrame` tactic. This tactic is a powerful but fast way to find the parts of the goal that can be framed immediately and also terminates if all parts of the goal can be framed. The second derivation (after the `Restart.`) of the Iris proof demonstrates this use.

Chapter 3

Demonstration of `link`

As an alternative to, or in concert with, using the Iris Framework, a proposition in separation logic can be proven by linking using our `link` tactic. Linking is similar to framing, where you ‘cancel out’ two subterms in a formula. Unlike framing, however, `link` does not require that exactly one of the terms is in the context. The `link` tactic can also cancel deeply nested terms, though there are still some requirements.

The standard way to use our `link` tactic is to provide it three *paths*: the *shared path* \vec{p}_c , *left path* \vec{p}_l and *right path* \vec{p}_r . These paths are highlighted in Figures 3.1 and 3.2 with a black underline, blue overline and red overline respectively. These highlights show the term that can be obtained by following the corresponding path. As seen in the figures, these paths are lists of directions `Left` (\mathbb{L}) or `Right` (\mathbb{R}). The path \vec{p}_c is interpreted as directions from the top-level connective of the goal term to the first common ancestor connective of the two terms we want to link, the *linking terms*. We call the subformula where this least common ancestor connective is the top-level connective the *kernel*. The other two paths \vec{p}_l and \vec{p}_r are the directions to the desired linking propositions *from the left and right hand sides* of the selected first common ancestor connective.

3.1 Demonstration on Propositional Separation Logic

Let us walk through the proof steps of a proof of the proposition $((P \multimap P) \multimap Q \ast (Q \multimap R \ast S \ast U)) \multimap T \multimap S \ast U \ast R \ast T$ that uses linking, displayed in Figure 3.1.

- 7: We first choose to link the terms T at line 7. To see that the T 's can be canceled, notice that we could have introduced the wands twice to get the left T in our context, which we could then cancel by framing the left over goal $S \ast U \ast R \ast T$. Our `link` tactic does this framing similarly, but leaves the rest of the goal mostly undisturbed.
- 10: At line 10 we pick the linking terms P . If you look from the top connective, these terms P are to the left of a wand twice. This is important. A proposition $(P \multimap P) \multimap \text{Emp}$ does not hold in general, but a proposition $((P \multimap P) \multimap \text{Emp}) \multimap \text{Emp}$ does. In general, the path \vec{p}_c can only point to a term with a wand as the top-level connective if the path points to the left of a wand an *even* number of times. We call this type of link a *backward link*.
- 13: Next, we link the terms Q at line 13. Notice that the path \vec{p}_c goes to the left of a wand once, and the top-level connective is a separating conjunction. Think of this type of link as kind of forward reasoning, where we provide the proof of Q for the term $Q \multimap R \ast S \ast U$ before we use any of the resulting terms R , S or U . In general,

```

1 Lemma demo1 (PROP : bi) (P Q R S T : PROP) :
2   ((P -* P) -* Q * (Q -* R * S * U)) -*
3   T -*
4   S * U * R * T.
5 Proof.
6   (* ((P -* P) -* Q * (Q -* R * S * U)) -*  $\overline{T}$  -* S * U * R *  $\overline{T}$  *)
7   link [Right],  $\overline{[]}$  [Right; Right; Right].
8
9   (* ( $\overline{P}$  -*  $\overline{P}$ ) -* Q * (Q -* R * S * U) -* S * U * R *)
10  link [Left; Left],  $\overline{[]}$   $\overline{[]}$ .
11
12  (*  $\overline{Q}$  * ( $\overline{Q}$  -* R * S * U) -* S * U * R *)
13  link [Left],  $\overline{[]}$   $\overline{[Left]}$ .
14
15  (*  $\overline{R}$  * S * U -* S * U *  $\overline{R}$  *)
16  link [],  $\overline{[Left]}$   $\overline{[Right; Right]}$ .
17
18  (*  $\overline{S}$  * U -* S *  $\overline{U}$  *)
19  link [],  $\overline{[]}$   $\overline{[]}$ .
20
21  (* emp *)
22  trivial.
23 Qed.

```

Figure 3.1: Proof of `demo1` using linking, with intermediate proof states interwoven in comments. The highlights in the Rocq code match the selected subformulas that is highlighted the same way in the intermediate proof states above that line of code.

the path \vec{p}_c can only point to a term with separating conjunction as the top-level connective if the path points to the left of a wand an *odd* number of times. We call this type of link a *forward link*.

- 16: The step at line 16 is straightforward, we create a backward link of the terms R .
- 19: Line 19 shows that the selected linking terms do not need to be atomic. As we will see in the next example, the linking terms only need to be unifiable.
- 22: The `link` tactic is not a terminating tactic. You will need a tactic such as `trivial` from Rocq or `done` from Iris to prove the final term. `link` enters the IPM, so applying `reflexivity` directly does not work.

3.2 Demonstration with Quantifiers

```

1 Lemma demo2 {τ1 τ2 : Type} (F : τ1 → PROP) (G : τ1 → τ2 → PROP) (H : τ2 → PROP)
2   (f : τ2 → τ1) (v : τ2):
3   F (f v) -*
4   (∀ x : τ1, F x -* ∃ y : τ2, G x y * H v) -*
5   ∃ y z, H z * G (f z) y.
6 Proof.
7   (* F (f v) -*
8     (∀ x, F x -* ∃ y, G x y * H v -* ∃ y z, H z * G (f z) y *)
9   link [Right], [Right;Left] [Right].
10
11  (* F (f v) -* ∃ x, F (f x) * * ∀ _ : τ2, H v -* H x * *)
12  link [], [] [Left].
13
14  (* ∀ _ : τ2, H v -* H v * *)
15  link [], [] [].
16
17  (* emp *)
18  trivial.
19 Qed.

```

Figure 3.2: Proof of `demo2` using linking. The intermediate states and highlights are displayed similar to Figure 3.1

Our `link` tactic also works under quantifiers. To show this, we consider the proposition $F(f v) \multimap (\forall x : \tau_1. F x \multimap \exists y : \tau_2. G x y * H v) \multimap \exists y z. H z * G(f z) y$ in Figure 3.2 step-by-step. In this thesis all functions and variables, such as f and v in this example, are implicitly universally bound.

9: For the linking of the terms G at line 9, notice that the left term $G x y$ is under a universal quantification $(\forall x : \tau_1)$ to the left of an arrow. Normally, if we wanted to use this term, we would have to provide such an $x : \tau_1$ after adding it to the context. Similarly, we see that the term $G(f z) y$ is under two existential quantifications $(\exists y : \tau_2. \exists z : \tau_1)$ to the right of the arrows. Again, in order to prove this goal, we would normally first search for and provide instances $y : \tau_2, z : \tau_1$ for which the goal holds. Linking allows us to reduce these terms without providing these quantifiers directly. Instead, we assert that they are instantiable and let the system figure out what the new goal should be that would make this hold.

12: Line 12 shows that quantifiers that are in the Rocq context can be used for this instantiation. The tactic will find the $v : \tau_2$ that is in the context and introduce the existential automatically.

15: Finally, line 15 of the proof shows that a path implicitly ‘enters’ a quantifier.

3.3 Cleanup without Information Loss

Apart from removing the linking terms, the desired result of an application of `link` is a goal that is simple as possible, but without any loss of information. In order to achieve this, most occurrences of `Emp` the tactic encounters are cleaned up automatically, if it possible to do so without losing information. For example, linking the propositions P in a goal $(\text{Emp} \multimap P \multimap (P \multimap \text{Emp})) \multimap \text{Emp}$ results in the term `Emp` immediately. Under quantifiers this cleanup is also attempted, and is once again only done if it leads to no loss of information. Consider, for example, the intermediate proof state at line 14 show in `demo2`. If we consider it in isolation, an application of `link` should give the new goal $\forall _ : \tau_2. \text{Emp}$ instead of just `Emp`, because this term also provides the information that τ_2 is inhabited. In the demonstration, however, we already know τ_2 is inhabited, because there is a $v : \tau_2$ in the context. An application of `link` is therefore allowed to remove the quantifier entirely. If there had been no such inhabitant in the context, the new goal would have been $\forall _ : \tau_2. \text{Emp}$.

3.4 Pitfalls

Sometimes the new goal resulting from a link might not be what you expected or even provable. In this section are some of these unexpected or unprovable cases:

Unexpected Changes to the Rest of the Goal As we have seen in `demo2`, the new goal that results from linking may be changed by more than just the removal of the linking terms. For terms that do not use quantifiers this is also possible. For example, if we link the two terms P_3 in the proposition $P_1 * P_2 * P_3 \multimap P_3 * P_2 * P_1$, the result is slightly unexpected. If we had just removed the terms P_3 , we would have been left with a new goal $P_1 * P_2 \multimap P_1 * P_2$. Instead, we are left with a new goal $P_1 \multimap P_2 \multimap P_1 * P_2$. Luckily, this is not a problem, as it is equiderivable to the expected proposition. The exact reason for this we discuss in Section 4.4. You will encounter this if you cancel terms in a chain of separating conjunctions that is to the left of a wand.

Unprovable New Goal Similar to when one tries to eliminate an existential quantifier too soon in many systems, choosing the wrong propositions to link will sometimes create a goal that is unprovable. For example, if we had attempted to link the proposition R at line 13 of `demo1`, this would have generated the new goal $Q \multimap S * U * Q * (S * U \multimap \text{Emp})$. This is not provable, as the proposition $(S * U \multimap \text{Emp})$ is in a separate part of the memory from both S and U , so they cannot be linked. In general, when a context contains a term that $P \multimap Q * R$, and P can be linked to a formula in that same context, then linking either Q or R will usually result in an unprovable goal. Instead, the proposition P should be reduced by forward links until $Q * R$ are no longer behind a wand.

3.5 Automatically Searching Paths

Once the tactic has been given a path \vec{p}_c , our `link` tactic can automatically search for paths \vec{p}_l and \vec{p}_r that would result in a valid link. These arguments can therefore optionally be left out. This will, however, rely on backtracking, and will only fail when all possible orders of linking rules from Section 4.4 have been considered, so it is not great for performance. Alternatively or additionally, we often want to link at the top-level, with $\vec{p}_c = []$, so leaving out that argument will implicitly use the empty list for \vec{p}_c . We therefore have four ‘modes’ for the link tactic:

```

1 Lemma demo1 (PROP : bi) (P Q R S T U : PROP) :
2 ((P -* P) -* Q * (Q -* R * S * U)) -* T -* S * U * R * T.
3 Proof.
4 (* ((P -* P) -* Q * (Q -* R * S * U)) -* T -* S * U * R * T *)
5 repeat link.
6 (* S * U * (P -* P) * (Q -* Q * (S * U -* emp)) *)
7 (* This goal is unprovable, so we restart *)
8 Restart.
9 (* ((P -* P) -* Q * (Q -* R * S * U)) -* T -* S * U * R * T *)
10 link [Left; Right].
11
12 (* ((P -* P) -* R * S * U) -* T -* S * U * R * T *)
13 link [Left;Left].
14
15 (* R * S * U -* T -* S * U * R * T *)
16 by repeat link.
17 Qed.

```

Figure 3.3: Proof of demo_1 using automatic search.

- **link cp lp rp:** Calling the tactic with three arguments implies all 3 paths are provided. This is the default mode, so none of the paths are searched for or inferred.
- **link lp rp:** Calling the tactic with two arguments is interpreted as a link where the top-level connective is the kernel, so $\vec{p}_c = []$ is inferred.
- **link cp:** Calling the tactic with one argument is interpreted as a link where only the path to the kernel is provided, and the other two paths have to be searched for using backtracking.
- **link:** Calling the tactic with no arguments will both infer that $\vec{p}_c = []$ and search for the other two paths using backtracking.

Finally, you could only provide one of the paths \vec{p}_l or \vec{p}_r and tell the system to search for the other path by replacing that path with an underscore in its place. For example ‘`link [] [Left] _`’ will only search for a path \vec{p}_r . Leaving \vec{p}_c empty will sadly not search for a path that results in a valid link and will likely fail.

Some somewhat large propositions that might not necessarily be hard to prove, but could be mechanically intensive, are often easily solved with repeated linking. For example, we can prove the proposition $(L * ((M * ((N * O) -* P) -* Q) -* R)) -* (O * ((M * (N -* P)) -* Q)) -* R * L$ with the line ‘`by repeat link`’. Using `repeat link` will not, however, solve the pitfall described in Section 3.4 of generating unprovable goals and will only ever link at top-level. Figure 3.3 shows how this automatic search might be used for demo_1 and when it does not work.

```

1 Lemma demo3 (PROP : bi) (τ1 τ2 : Type) (F : τ1 → PROP) (G : τ2 → PROP) (P : PROP):
2   ⊢ (P * (∃ a, F a)) * ((P * (∃ a, F a)) -* (∃ x, G x)) -* (∃ x, G x).
3 Proof.
4   iIntros "[[HP HL] HR]".
5   (* "HP" : P
6     "HL" : ∃ a : τ1, F a
7     "HR" : P * (∃ a : τ1, F a) -* ∃ x : τ2, G x
8     -----*
9     ∃ x : τ2, G x *)
10  link_hyps "HL" "HR" [] [Left; Right] as "H".
11  (* "HP" : P
12    "H" : ∃ _ : τ1, P -* ∃ x : τ2, G x
13    -----*
14    ∃ x : τ2, G x *)
15  link_hyps "HP" "H" as "H".
16  (* "H" : ∃ (_ : τ1) (x : τ2), G x
17    -----*
18    ∃ x : τ2, G x *)
19  link_to "H" [] [].
20  (* ∀ _ : τ2, emp *)
21  done.
22 Qed.

```

Figure 3.4: Proof of `demo3` using standard linking and linking with the spatial context.

3.6 Interacting with Iris Proof Mode

Even though an application of our `link` tactic enters the Iris Proof Mode, it does not interact with the spatial context at all. For this use case, there are two different tactics: `link.to` and `link.hyps`. Our `link.to` tactic links a subformula from the goal to a subformula from a selected hypothesis, which is therefore always a backward link. Similarly, `link.hyps` allows us to link two propositions in two hypothesis with each other, which is therefore always a forward link. See Figure 3.4 for a derivation containing both. Note that the least common ancestor connective in these cases is effectively always the long, above-top-level wand from Iris Proof Mode in the case of `link.to` or a separating conjunction before a wand for `link.hyps`, so no \vec{p}_c can be provided. Like for our `link` tactic, the other paths can be automatically inferred and are done so if no paths are provided.

Chapter 4

Inference System

In this chapter we discuss the mathematical foundations of our `link` tactic. Given a goal proposition G and three paths \vec{p}_c , \vec{p}_l and \vec{p}_r that together yield linking terms L_L and L_R , we want to find a simplified goal G_{Simp} such that $G_{Simp} \vdash G$ and neither of these occurrences of L_L and L_R occur in G_{Simp} . The procedure is split up in three steps. In Section 4.1 we relate these steps to a single application of `link` from the example derivation `demo1` from Figure 3.1. Then, in Section 4.2 we introduce make some general statements about the judgments we define in the later sections. Finally, in Sections 4.3 to 4.5 we discuss the individual steps in more depth.

4.1 An Example of the Procedure

Let us consider the intermediate proof state $G = Q * (Q \multimap R * S * U) \multimap S * U * R$ shown at line 12 of Figure 3.1 and what happens when we apply `link [Left] [] [Left]`. The procedure can be split into three steps:

1. **Splitting from the Context:** The first step of the procedure, which we discuss in detail in Section 4.3, is to find a term $Kern$ (the kernel) and a context $\mathcal{C}\{\}$ such that $G \dashv\vdash \mathcal{C}\{Kern\}$ and the least common ancestor connective of the linking terms is the top-most connective of the kernel. In our example, the path to the kernel is $\vec{p}_c = [L]$, so in this case that would create a kernel $Kern = Q * (Q \multimap R * S * U)$ and a context $\mathcal{C}_\setminus\{X\} = X \multimap S * U * R$. We will see that these context functions can be either *monotone* ($\mathcal{C}_\setminus\{\}$) or *antimonotone* ($\mathcal{C}_\setminus\{\}$), and that this corresponds directly to the link being a backward link or forward link, respectively.
2. **Simplification of the Kernel:** Next, in Section 4.4 we discuss how to simplify the kernel to a term $Kern_{Simp}$, such that $Kern_{Simp} \vdash Kern$ for a monotone context $\mathcal{C}_\setminus\{\}$ or $Kern \vdash Kern_{Simp}$ for an antimonotone context $\mathcal{C}_\setminus\{\}$. Since the paths \vec{p}_l and \vec{p}_r from our example point to the propositions Q , this might reduce the term $Kern = Q * (Q \multimap R * S * U)$ to $Kern_{Simp} = R * S * U$. Most of the interesting mathematics will be in this section.
3. **Cleaning up:** Finally in Section 4.5 we create the simplified goal G_{Simp} by putting the simplified $Kern_{Simp}$ in the context calculated previously, and cleaning up most redundant occurrences of `Emp`. In the example, no additional cleaning up is required, so we simply yield $G_{Simp} = \mathcal{C}_\setminus\{Kern_{Simp}\} = R * S * U \multimap S * U * R$. If, instead, the context function had been $\mathcal{C}_\setminus\{X\} = (\text{Emp} * (\text{Emp} \multimap X)) \multimap S * U * R$, for example, these additional occurrences of `Emp` would have been cleaned up during this step, resulting in the same simplified goal.

4.2 Judgments for Proof Search

In this chapter we define many judgments for the various procedures. These judgments can be thought of as *type classes* from Rocq, which are explained in Section 5.1. These judgments will therefore have a semantic definition and the rules defined on these judgments can be derived semantically, making the system automatically sound.

The judgments use square brackets $[\dots]$ to indicate some sort of ‘output’ and the rest of the propositions, paths, etc, in the judgment outside of these braces are ‘input’. For those familiar with Rocq’s type classes, this corresponds to using an *ev* in the place of an output. Additionally, we use angle braces $\langle n \rangle$ next to each rule to indicate a *cost* of n for that rule. If during proof search multiple rules can be applied, any of the rules with the lowest cost should be used.

4.3 Splitting from the Context

The core of the linking procedure we will define in Section 4.4 argues about the kernel as if it were the entire goal. As we saw before, when we want to link two terms where the kernel is strictly a subformula of the goal, we therefore split the goal into a kernel and some sort of a *context function*. Consider, as a different example, the goal EG :

$$EG \triangleq (P * (P -* Q)) -* Q$$

If we want to link the propositions Q , the kernel is the goal already, so we could immediately move on to the next step. If we want to link the propositions P , however, the kernel is the left-most $*$. In order to move on to the next step, we first need to split this subformula from the rest of the formula.

In order to do this without losing the information the rest of the formula provides, we create context functions $\mathcal{C}\{\} : Prop \rightarrow Prop$. In the example proposition EG , this function could look like $EC_{\setminus}\{X\} = X -* Q$, and the ‘split’ proposition would then be $EKern$:

$$EKern \triangleq P * (P -* Q)$$

Our goal, in this example, is to find a simplified proposition EG_{Simp} that does not contain the ‘selected’ occurrences of our linking propositions P , such that $EG_{Simp} \vdash EG$. We have to be careful when simplifying the kernel, however, because the monotonicity of our context functions affects whether we should look for a simplification $Kern_{Simp} \vdash Kern$ or $Kern \vdash Kern_{Simp}$. In our example, the context function $EC_{\setminus}\{\}$ is not *monotone* (\nearrow), but *antimonotone* (\searrow):

$$Monotone(\mathcal{C}\{\}) \triangleq \forall PQ. (P \vdash Q) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}\{P\} \vdash \mathcal{C}\{Q\} \quad (4.1)$$

$$Antimonotone(\mathcal{C}\{\}) \triangleq \forall PQ. (Q \vdash P) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}\{P\} \vdash \mathcal{C}\{Q\} \quad (4.2)$$

$$\mathcal{C}_m\{\} \triangleq \left\{ \mathcal{C}\{\} : Prop \rightarrow Prop \mid \begin{array}{ll} Monotone(\mathcal{C}\{\}) & \text{if } m = \nearrow \\ Antimonotone(\mathcal{C}\{\}) & \text{if } m = \searrow \end{array} \right\} \quad (4.3)$$

We also use notation of a line above a monotonicity to indicate the reverse polarity monotonicity, so a context function $\mathcal{C}_{\overline{m}}\{\}$ has monotone polarity if $m = \searrow$ and antimonotone polarity if $m = \nearrow$.

Since our example context is antimonotone, we need to find $EKern_{Simp}$, such that $EKern \vdash EKern_{Simp}$ to get our final simplified $EG_{Simp} = EC_{\setminus}\{EKern_{Simp}\} \vdash EC_{\setminus}\{EKern\} = EG$.

In general, if we have a proposition $Kern$ where the top-level connective is the kernel, and a context function $\mathcal{C}\{\}$ such that $G = \mathcal{C}\{Kern\}$, we need to prove $Kern \vdash Kern_{Simp}$ if $Monotone(\mathcal{C}\{\})$, which we call a *backward link*, and $Kern_{Simp} \vdash Kern$ if $Antimonotone(\mathcal{C}\{\})$, which we call a *forward link*.

SPLIT-BASE

$$\frac{}{P \dashv\equiv [id_{\surd}\{P\}]} \langle 1 \rangle$$

<p>SPLIT*\mathbb{L}</p> $\frac{Q \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]}{Q * R \dashv\equiv^{\mathbb{L}::\vec{p}_c} [(\lambda X. \mathcal{C}_m\{X\} * R)_m\{P\}]} \langle 0 \rangle$	<p>SPLIT*\mathbb{R}</p> $\frac{R \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]}{Q * R \dashv\equiv^{\mathbb{R}::\vec{p}_c} [(\lambda X. Q * \mathcal{C}_m\{X\})_m\{P\}]} \langle 0 \rangle$
<p>SPLIT*\mathbb{L}</p> $\frac{Q \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]}{Q -* R \dashv\equiv^{\mathbb{L}::\vec{p}_c} [(\lambda X. \mathcal{C}_m\{X\} -* R)_{\overline{m}}\{Q\}]} \langle 0 \rangle$	<p>SPLIT*\mathbb{R}</p> $\frac{R \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]}{Q -* R \dashv\equiv^{\mathbb{R}::\vec{p}_c} [(\lambda X. Q -* \mathcal{C}_m\{X\})_m\{Q\}]} \langle 0 \rangle$
<p>SPLIT\forall</p> $\frac{\forall x. Q \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]}{\forall x. Q \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [(\lambda X. \forall x. \mathcal{C}_m\{X\})_m\{P\}]} \langle 0 \rangle$	<p>SPLIT\exists</p> $\frac{\forall x. Q \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]}{\exists x. Q \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [(\lambda X. \exists x. \mathcal{C}_m\{X\})_m\{P\}]} \langle 0 \rangle$

Figure 4.1: Rules for the splitting judgment. The identity context $id\{\}$ is $\lambda X.X$

$$\frac{}{P -* P \dashv\equiv [id_{\surd}\{P -* P\}]} \text{SPLIT-BASE}$$

$$\frac{}{(P -* P) -* Q \dashv\equiv^{\mathbb{L}} [\lambda X. (X -* Q)_{\surd}\{P -* P\}]} \text{SPLIT*}\mathbb{L}$$

$$\frac{\forall x. R * ((P -* P) -* Q) \dashv\equiv^{\mathbb{R}:\mathbb{L}} [\lambda X. (R * (X -* Q))_{\surd}\{P -* P\}]}{\forall x. R * ((P -* P) -* Q) \dashv\equiv^{\mathbb{R}:\mathbb{L}} [(\lambda X. \forall x. R * (X -* Q))_{\surd}\{P -* P\}]} \text{SPLIT}\forall$$

Figure 4.2: Example derivation of splitting $P -* P$ from a proposition $\forall x. R * ((P -* P) -* Q)$. The context functions are simplified for readability. In reality, these context functions would be nested applications.

Rules of Splitting from the Context We define the *splitting judgment*, which uses notation $Q \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]$. Semantically it says that $Q \dashv\vdash \mathcal{C}_m\{P\}$ and that P is obtained from following path \vec{p}_c . We call a derivation of $Q \dashv\equiv^{\vec{p}_c} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]$ a *split*.

Figure 4.1 shows the rules used to derive this judgment and Figure 4.2 displays an example derivation. Each non-terminating rule says that if we have a context $\mathcal{C}\{\}$ and terms P, Q such that $P \dashv\vdash \mathcal{C}\{Q\}$, we can add a connective to both P and the context function and the equivalence will still hold.

For all of these rules except SPLIT* \mathbb{L} and SPLIT-BASE, the monotonicity of the context in the antecedent is the same as the monotonicity of the new context function in the consequent. For the rule SPLIT* \mathbb{L} , the context switches polarity of monotonicity, which is highlighted in red and blue by the subscripts of the contexts in this rule. Clearly the context $id\{\}$ of the base case is monotone, as it is the identity function.

During proof search, whenever a binary connective is at the top level, we use the path \vec{p}_c to choose a direction by matching the rule to the head of \vec{p}_c . Afterwards, we move on with the proof with the tail of \vec{p}_c .

Since we require the final top-level connective to be either a wand or a separating

conjunction, whenever we encounter a quantification we do should not use the SPLIT-BASE rule, even if the path is the empty list. We use our cost system to enforce this, the base rule has a cost higher than the quantifier rules, so it will not be used if the top level connective is a quantifier. The cost of the other rules does not matter, as they are disambiguated by the path.

Splitting with Quantifiers The rules from Figure 4.1 are slightly oversimplified, especially the rules for the quantifiers SPLIT \forall and SPLIT \exists , which are technically not sound as presented. Since the quantifier x can occur anywhere in Q , it can also occur in the kernel P . If, for example, the proposition P in Figure 4.2 was replaced by $f x$ instead, then the conclusion would look like

$$\forall x. R * ((f x -* f x) -* Q) \stackrel{[\mathbb{R};\mathbb{L}]}{\models} [(\lambda X. \forall x. R * (X -* Q)) \searrow \{f x -* f x\}]$$

This is a problem because the x is not bound in the kernel $f x -* f x$ that is highlighted red in this example. The problem is further enhanced if we use dependent types. We fix this problem by changing the type of context functions to allow functions as arguments, so that we can bind the kernel with a function argument. This has some knock-on effects, as we have to change the definition of monotonicity and the judgments themselves as well. We discuss how we solve this problem by using telescopic binding of both the judgment and the monotonicity functions in Section 5.3.

4.4 Simplification of the Kernel

In Section 4.3 we computed a kernel $Kern$ where the top-most connective separates the two linking propositions L_L and L_R and we computed a context $\mathcal{C}_m\{\}$ with $m \in \{\nearrow, \searrow\}$. In this step we compute a simplified kernel $Kern_{Simp}$, such that $Kern_{Simp} \vdash Kern$ if $m = \nearrow$, or $Kern \vdash Kern_{Simp}$ if $m = \searrow$.

The procedure in this step considers two judgments: the *backward linking judgment* and the *forward linking judgment*.

$\dashv\ast$: The backward linking judgment uses the following notation:

$$[P] \vDash Q \dashv\ast R$$

This judgment is semantically equivalent to $P \vdash Q \dashv\ast R$. We can combine this judgment with the splitting judgment to get the inference rule LINK-BACKWARD-SIMPLE

$$\frac{\text{LINK-BACKWARD-SIMPLE} \quad G \stackrel{\vec{p}_c}{\models} [\mathcal{C}_{\nearrow}\{Q \dashv\ast R\}] \quad [Kern_{Simp}] \vDash Q \dashv\ast R \quad \vdash \mathcal{C}_{\nearrow}\{Kern_{Simp}\}}{\vdash G}$$

\ast : The forward linking judgment uses the following notation:

$$Q \ast R \vDash [P]$$

This judgment is semantically equivalent to $Q \ast R \vdash P$. We can also combine this judgment with the splitting judgment to get the inference rule LINK-FORWARD-SIMPLE

$$\frac{\text{LINK-FORWARD-SIMPLE} \quad G \stackrel{\vec{p}_c}{\models} [\mathcal{C}_{\searrow}\{Q \ast R\}] \quad Q \ast R \vDash [Kern_{Simp}] \quad \vdash \mathcal{C}_{\searrow}\{Kern_{Simp}\}}{\vdash G}$$

Terminal rule

$$\text{LINK-REFL} \quad \frac{}{[\text{Emp}] \models P \multimap P} \langle 0 \rangle$$

Right Backward ($[\dots] \models Q \multimap \dots$) rules

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-RB*L} \\ \frac{[P] \models Q \multimap R_L}{[P * R_R] \models Q \multimap R_L * R_R} \langle 10 \rangle \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-RB*R} \\ \frac{[P] \models Q \multimap R_R}{[R_L * P] \models Q \multimap R_L * R_R} \langle 10 \rangle \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-RB*L} \\ \frac{Q * R_L \models [P]}{[P \multimap R_R] \models Q \multimap R_L \multimap R_R} \langle 1 \rangle \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-RB*R} \\ \frac{[P] \models Q \multimap R_R}{[R_L \multimap P] \models Q \multimap R_L \multimap R_R} \langle 2 \rangle \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-RB}\forall \\ \frac{\forall x. [P] \models Q \multimap R}{[\forall x.P] \models Q \multimap \forall x.R} \langle 1 \rangle \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-RB}\exists\text{-QU} \\ \frac{\forall \vec{y} : \vec{\tau}. [P] \models Q \multimap R[x := t]}{[\exists \vec{y} : \vec{\tau}. P] \models Q \multimap \exists x.R} \langle 1 \rangle \end{array}$$

Left Backward ($[\dots] \models \dots \multimap R$) rules

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-LB*L} \\ \frac{[P] \models Q_L \multimap R}{[Q_R \multimap P] \models Q_L * Q_R \multimap R} \langle 1 \rangle \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-LB*R} \\ \frac{[P] \models Q_R \multimap R}{[Q_L \multimap P] \models Q_L * Q_R \multimap R} \langle 1 \rangle \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-LB*} \\ \frac{[P] \models Q_R \multimap R}{[Q_L * P] \models Q_L \multimap Q_R \multimap R} \langle 10 \rangle \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-LB}\exists \\ \frac{\forall x. [P] \models Q \multimap R}{[\forall x.P] \models \exists x.Q \multimap R} \langle 1 \rangle \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{LINK-LB}\forall\text{-QU} \\ \frac{\forall \vec{y} : \vec{\tau}. [P] \models Q[x := t] \multimap R}{[\exists \vec{y} : \vec{\tau}. P] \models \forall x.Q \multimap R} \langle 5 \rangle \end{array}$$

Figure 4.3: Inference rules for the backward linking judgment ($[Kern_{Simp}] \models Q \multimap R$).

Both judgments should be interpreted to say that the output term P is a simplified form of the input term $Q \multimap R$ or $Q * R$, such that the selected occurrences of L_L and L_R no longer occur in P , and that if the simplified P holds in separation logic, then so does the input term.

The inference rules to derive these judgments are given in Figures 4.3 and 4.4 and are mutually recursive due to the polarity switch in the wand.

4.4.1 Rules for Backward Linking Judgments

Figure 4.3 Shows the rules to derive a backward judgment. In this subsection we discuss most of these backward rules individually in the next three paragraphs, except the rules tagged with a trailing ‘-QU’. Those rules are discussed in Section 4.4.3.

The Terminal Rule The terminal rule LINK-REFL is a backward judgment and is the only terminal rule in the system. This is the only rule where the selected propositioned actually get ‘cancelled’, all other rules are there to ‘move’ the non-linking propositions out

of the way. Since it is the only terminal rule, if we are able to prove a linking judgment, that automatically means we have found a term without the linking propositions.

Right Backward Rules As we will see more often, the rules $\text{LINK-RB}^*\mathbb{L}$ and $\text{LINK-RB}^*\mathbb{R}$ appear simple but are slightly tricky. Unlike some of the rules, the premise and the conclusion of these rules are not equiderivable. We call this type of rule *synchronous*, and discuss the effect of this in a later paragraph about non-determinism. Like all of the rules for binary connectives, they ‘move’ the term that does not contain the linking proposition to the simplified proposition, taking care not to switch sides so the simplified term $Kern_{Simp}$ looks as similar as possible to the original term $Kern$. This rule also causes the slightly unexpected simplification described in the first paragraph of Section 3.4, as the generated output does contain a separating conjunction.

The rule $\text{LINK-RB}^*\mathbb{R}$ is similar and less tricky. The premise and conclusion of this rule are equiderivable, which we call an *asynchronous* rule.

The rule $\text{LINK-RB}^*\mathbb{L}$ is the only backward rule that requires the proof of a forward judgment. This is because, as we have seen, moving to the left of a wand changes monotonicity of the context. While we do not explicitly use context functions when simplifying, backward linking judgments always implicitly assume they are used in a monotone context, and forward linking judgments assume antimonotone contexts, which should also be clear from the direction of the entailment. This rule is crucial for backward links that are nested to the left of a wand multiple times.

The rule $\text{LINK-RB}\forall$ uses the \forall notation we discussed before in Section 2.3, where you can assume the appropriate side conditions for the quantifiers. The rule is another asynchronous rule. It eliminates the quantifier entirely, which is possible since it does not occur in Q because of the implicit side conditions.

Left Backward Rules For those familiar with subformula linking in intuitionistic logics, the rules $\text{LINK-LB}^*\mathbb{L}$ and $\text{LINK-LB}^*\mathbb{R}$ might seem surprising. In such systems, the proposition that does not contain the linking proposition is not added to the simplified term at all. Instead, a system such as Actema relies on contraction to never remove any assumption. In our case, since we do not have weakening, we add the unused proposition to the simplified term. This will have a negative effect on the non-determinism we discuss in a later paragraph.

Unlike all the other rules for binary connectives, there is no \mathbb{L} variant of the Left Backward $-*$ rule, only a \mathbb{R} version, LINK-LB^* , which is straightforward but synchronous. We could add a \mathbb{L} rule that switches monotonicity like $\text{LINK-RB}^*\mathbb{L}$ and adds the unused term to the simplified term in a manner similar to the previous two rules. This creates additional non-determinism problem similar to the previous two terms as well, however, so we would rather avoid it. Luckily, it is possible to leave it out entirely without breaking the system. This is because we need to end up at a valid terminal rule, and therefore both sides of the judgment must go the the back of a wand for a valid link. Since the rule $\text{LINK-RB}^*\mathbb{L}$ switches polarity, we can allow the forward rules to switch polarity back.

The rule $\text{LINK-LB}\exists$ is similar to $\text{LINK-RB}\forall$, effectively introducing the quantifier for the rest of the proof.

4.4.2 Rules for Forward Linking Judgments

Figure 4.4 shows the rules to derive a forward linking judgment

The left forward rules are all basically symmetric counterparts to the right forward rules, so we mention only the right forward rules in this section, and the counterpart is implied to behave the same.

Right Forward ($Q * \dots \models [\dots]$) rules

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-RF*}\mathbb{L} \\
\frac{Q * R_{\mathbb{L}} \models [P]}{Q * R_{\mathbb{L}} * R_{\mathbb{R}} \models [P * R_{\mathbb{R}}]} \langle 1 \rangle
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-RF*}\mathbb{R} \\
\frac{Q * R_{\mathbb{R}} \models [P]}{Q * R_{\mathbb{L}} * R_{\mathbb{R}} \models [R_{\mathbb{L}} * P]} \langle 1 \rangle
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-RF-}\mathbb{L} \\
\frac{[P] \models Q \multimap R_{\mathbb{L}}}{Q * R_{\mathbb{L}} \multimap R_{\mathbb{R}} \models [P \multimap R_{\mathbb{R}}]} \langle 5 \rangle
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-RF-}\mathbb{R} \\
\frac{Q * R_{\mathbb{R}} \models [P]}{Q * R_{\mathbb{L}} \multimap R_{\mathbb{R}} \models [R_{\mathbb{L}} \multimap P]} \langle 5 \rangle
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-RF}\exists \\
\frac{\forall x. Q * R \models [P]}{Q * \exists x. R \models [\exists x. P]} \langle 1 \rangle
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-RF}\forall\text{-QU} \\
\frac{\forall \vec{y} : \vec{\tau}. Q * R[x := t] \models [P]}{Q * \forall x. R \models [\forall \vec{y} : \vec{\tau}. P]} \langle 5 \rangle
\end{array}$$

Left Forward ($\dots * R \models [\dots]$) rules

(These are basically the symmetric counterparts of the Right Forward rules)

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-LF*}\mathbb{L} \\
\frac{Q_{\mathbb{L}} * R \models [P]}{Q_{\mathbb{L}} * Q_{\mathbb{R}} * R \models [P * Q_{\mathbb{R}}]} \langle 1 \rangle
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-LF*}\mathbb{R} \\
\frac{Q_{\mathbb{R}} * R \models [P]}{Q_{\mathbb{L}} * Q_{\mathbb{R}} * R \models [Q_{\mathbb{L}} * P]} \langle 1 \rangle
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-LF-}\mathbb{L} \\
\frac{[P] \models R \multimap Q_{\mathbb{L}}}{Q_{\mathbb{L}} \multimap Q_{\mathbb{R}} * R \models [P \multimap Q_{\mathbb{R}}]} \langle 5 \rangle
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-LF-}\mathbb{R} \\
\frac{Q_{\mathbb{R}} * R \models [P]}{Q_{\mathbb{L}} \multimap Q_{\mathbb{R}} * R \models [Q_{\mathbb{L}} \multimap P]} \langle 5 \rangle
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-LF}\exists \\
\frac{\forall x. Q * R \models [P]}{(\exists x. Q) * R \models [\exists x. P]} \langle 1 \rangle
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-LF}\forall\text{-QU} \\
\frac{\forall \vec{y} : \vec{\tau}. Q[x := t] * R \models [P]}{\forall x. Q * R \models [\forall \vec{y} : \vec{\tau}. P]} \langle 5 \rangle
\end{array}$$

Figure 4.4: Inference rules for the forward linking judgment ($Q * R \models [Kern_{Simp}]$).

$$\begin{array}{c}
\vdots \\
\frac{\forall w. \quad \frac{[\top] \models Q(g u' v') w \multimap \exists z u v. Q(g u v) z}{\text{LINK-RB}\exists\text{-QU}(\vec{y} = [], t = w)}}{\text{LINK-LB}\exists} \\
\frac{\forall u' v'. \quad \frac{[\forall w. \top] \models \exists w. Q(g u' v') w \multimap \exists z u v. Q(g u v) z}{\text{LINK-LB}\forall\text{-QU}(\vec{y} = [u', v'], t = g u' v')}}{\text{LINK-LB}\forall\text{-QU}(\vec{y} = [u', v'], t = g u' v')} \\
\frac{}{[\exists u' v'. \forall w. \top] \models \forall x. \exists w. Q x w \multimap \exists z u v. Q(g u v) z}
\end{array}$$

Figure 4.5: Example derivation that uses rules LINK-RB \exists -QU and LINK-LB \forall -QU from Mulder and Krebbers [2024], modified for separation logic

The terminal rule LINK-REFL is the only terminal rule in the system. This rule is a backward linking judgment. Therefore, all forward links or judgments need to be turned into a backward judgment with the use of LINK-RF- $\ast\mathbb{L}$. This rule is similar to LINK-RB- $\ast\mathbb{L}$, in that it switches monotonicity because the linking term is to the left of a wand.

The rules LINK-LF- $\ast\mathbb{L}$, LINK-LF- $\ast\mathbb{R}$, LINK-LF- $\ast\mathbb{R}$ and LINK-LF \exists are all similar to the corresponding left *backward* rules, as they are both concerned with the same polarity context.

4.4.3 Quantifying the Uninstantiated

The rules that are tagged with a trailing ‘-QU’ all implement an idea called Quantifying the Uninstantiated from Mulder and Krebbers [2024], which allows for non-trivial quantifier instantiation. The idea of the QU rules is to quantify the quantifiers *soon enough*, so that they can be unified with quantifiers that were eliminated earlier in the process. It achieves this by defining a single rule that combines both instantiation and introduction of the quantifiers.

Figure 4.5 shows an example partial derivation from Mulder and Krebbers [2024] modified for separation logic that uses two of the QU rules. The key step is the application of LINK-LB \forall -QU with $\vec{y} = [u', v']$ and $t = g u' v'$, it both instantiates t and quantifies u' and v' in a single step. Upon inspection, choosing these values makes the arguments of Q match, which is required for LINK-REFL.

We see for the application of LINK-LB \forall -QU that both u' and v' need to be quantified and instantiated immediately, because we need to use the w from the existential that is under the left \forall before we can eliminate the first existential on the right.

Additionally, let us say the type of g in this example is $g : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2 \rightarrow \tau_3$. Since we need to instantiate both arguments immediately, this also means that the quantifiers in \vec{y} can be of different types $\vec{\tau}$.

How to automatically compute what the values of \vec{y} and t should be is discussed in-depth in Mulder and Krebbers [2024] and we will not do so in this thesis.

4.4.4 Non-determinism of the Rules

While performing proof search, we can usually apply a rule at either side of the \multimap or \ast . This choice corresponds to picking a left (backward/forward) or right (backward/forward) rule. Then, once we have chosen a side, if the top-level connective of that side is a binary connective, we usually also have to pick whether to use the \mathbb{L} or \mathbb{R} rule of that connective.

The second decision of picking the \mathbb{L} or \mathbb{R} rule can be answered by providing paths \vec{p}_l and \vec{p}_r in a way similar to how the path \vec{p}_c is used when splitting the context, but there is some nuance which we discuss in the next paragraph. If we do not provide any paths like we do in Section 3.5, however, the cost system with backtracking will find a link for us.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{[\text{Emp}] \models P \multimap P} \text{LINK-REFL} \\
\frac{}{[Q \multimap \text{Emp}] \models P * Q \multimap P} \text{LINK-LB*\mathbb{L}} \\
\frac{}{[Q * (Q \multimap \text{Emp})] \models P * Q \multimap Q * P} \text{LINK-RB*\mathbb{R}}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{[\text{Emp}] \models P \multimap P} \text{LINK-REFL} \\
\frac{}{[Q * \text{Emp}] \models P \multimap Q * P} \text{LINK-RB*\mathbb{R}} \\
\frac{}{[Q \multimap Q * \text{Emp}] \models P * Q \multimap Q * P} \text{LINK-LB*\mathbb{L}}
\end{array}$$

Figure 4.6: A pair of derivations that show that the rules LINK-RB*\mathbb{L} and LINK-LB*\mathbb{L} form a critical pair, where the application order matters.

The first decision is harder. We use heuristics and backtracking to make this decision, which we discuss in the paragraph after the next.

Paths for the Linking Judgments Each path points to a linking term L_L or L_R . During proof search we must ensure the paths keep pointing to these selected terms after each application of the rules. Unlike the rules for the splitting judgment, the rules we provide in Figures 4.3 and 4.4 do not show how we ensure this selection is preserved. This would add too much noise and it is mostly trivial. See, for example, what happens if we add the paths to the rules LINK-RB*\mathbb{L} and LINK-RB*\mathbb{R} in a similar fashion as the rules for the split judgment in rules LINK-RB*\mathbb{L}-WITH-PATHS and LINK-RB*\mathbb{R}-WITH-PATHS:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-RB*\mathbb{L}-WITH-PATHS} \\
\frac{[P] \models Q \vec{p}_l \multimap \vec{p}_r R_L}{[P * R_R] \models Q \vec{p}_l \multimap \mathbb{L}::\vec{p}_r R_L * R_R}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-RB*\mathbb{R}-WITH-PATHS} \\
\frac{[P] \models Q \vec{p}_l \multimap \vec{p}_r R_R}{[R_L * P] \models Q \vec{p}_l \multimap \mathbb{R}::\vec{p}_r R_L * R_R}
\end{array}$$

The only slightly interesting case is the rule LINK-LF*\mathbb{L}. This is the only rule where the order of the propositions Q_L and R necessarily swap with an application of the rule. To ensure the paths still point to the correct linking term, we therefore also have to swap the paths \vec{p}_l and \vec{p}_r when continuing with the proof search. The rule LINK-LF*\mathbb{L}-WITH-PATHS shows what it might look like if we added these paths to the rules LINK-LF*\mathbb{L}:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{LINK-LF*\mathbb{L}-WITH-PATHS} \\
\frac{[P] \models R \vec{p}_r \multimap \vec{p}_l Q_L}{Q_L \multimap Q_R \mathbb{L}::\vec{p}_l \multimap \vec{p}_r R \models [P \multimap Q_R]}
\end{array}$$

Further Non-determinism Choosing whether to apply a left or right rule, whether it is a forward rule or backward rule, is non-trivial. Even when following the directions of a path, the order of applying left or right rules can result in different terms $Kern_{Simp}$. For example, Figure 4.6 shows two possible derivations which show that linking the propositions P in $P * Q \multimap Q * P$ can result in either term $Kern_{Simp}^1 = Q * (Q \multimap \text{Emp})$ or $Kern_{Simp}^2 = Q \multimap Q * \text{Emp}$. Sometimes, this non-determinism is not a problem, where the terms $Kern_{Simp}$ are equiderivable. In this example, however, this is not the case. Even worse, $Kern_{Simp}^1$ is unprovable, as the resources Q are required for but separate from the term $(Q \multimap \text{Emp})$.

Like previous linking systems such as ProfInt, we can split up our rules into two categories:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{[\text{Emp}] \models P \multimap P} \text{LINK-REFL} \\
\frac{}{[Q * \text{Emp}] \models Q \multimap P \multimap P} \text{LINK-LB-*} \\
\frac{}{[(Q * \text{Emp}) * R] \models Q \multimap P \multimap P * R} \text{LINK-RB*\mathbb{L}}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{[\text{Emp}] \models P \multimap P} \text{LINK-REFL} \\
\frac{}{[\text{Emp} * R] \models P \multimap P * R} \text{LINK-RB*\mathbb{L}} \\
\frac{}{[Q * (\text{Emp} * R)] \models Q \multimap P \multimap P * R} \text{LINK-LB-*}
\end{array}$$

Figure 4.7: A pair of derivations that show using synchronous rules can still result in equiderivable terms

1. **Asynchronous rules:** Rules where the premise and conclusion are equiderivable are called asynchronous. Therefore, if a derivation requires only asynchronous rules (or the terminal rule), all possible resulting terms $\text{Kern}_{\text{Simp}}$ will be equiderivable. The asynchronous rules are:

Right Backward rules:	LINK-RB*\mathbb{L}	LINK-RB*\mathbb{R}	LINK-RB\forall
Left Backward rules:	LINK-LB*\mathbb{L}	LINK-LB*\mathbb{R}	LINK-LB\exists
Right Forward Rules:	LINK-RF*\mathbb{L}	LINK-RF*\mathbb{R}	LINK-RF\exists
Left Forward Rules:	LINK-LF*\mathbb{L}	LINK-LF*\mathbb{R}	LINK-LF\exists

2. **Synchronous rules:** Rules where the premise strictly entails the conclusion are called synchronous. The synchronous rules are the rest of the rules, so:

(Terminal rule:	LINK-REFL)		
Right Backward rules:	LINK-RB*\mathbb{L}	LINK-RB*\mathbb{R}	LINK-RB\exists-QU
Left Backward rules:	LINK-LB*		LINK-LB\forall-QU
Right Forward Rules:	LINK-RF*\mathbb{L}	LINK-RF*\mathbb{R}	LINK-RF\forall-QU
Left Forward Rules:	LINK-LF*\mathbb{L}	LINK-LF*\mathbb{R}	LINK-LF\forall-QU

As we have seen in Figure 4.6, the order in which the rules LINK-LB*\mathbb{L} and LINK-RB*\mathbb{R} are applied can result in two different terms that are not equiderivable. Not all combinations of synchronous rules are a problem in this way. For example, consider the derivation in Figure 4.7. Here we see that the order in which these two rules are applied do not matter, as the result is equiderivable by a single application of *-ASSOC.

Since the asynchronous rules never lose information, a good start for determining a rule order is to apply all these asynchronous rules first. After this, however, we use heuristics and backtracking to determine a rule order. The example highlighted in Section 3.4, where we wanted to link the propositions R in $Q * (Q \multimap R * S * U) \multimap S * U * R$, is a case where these heuristics result in an unprovable new goal. With different heuristics it is possible to create a term that *is* provable with the rules. For example, if we apply the rules LINK-LB*\mathbb{R}, LINK-LB*, LINK-LB*\mathbb{L}, LINK-RB*\mathbb{R}, LINK-RB*\mathbb{L} in that order from bottom to top, we get the new goal $Q \multimap Q * (S * U \multimap S * U * \text{Emp})$. We did not find a set of heuristics, however, where it was impossible to create an unprovable goal after linking.

Inference rules for the cleaning $*$ judgment: $Q * R \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [P] \iff Q * R \dashv\vdash P$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{CLEAN*}-\text{EMP-L} & \text{CLEAN*}-\text{EMP-R} & \text{CLEAN*}-\text{BASE} \\ \hline \text{Emp} * R \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [R] \langle 0 \rangle & Q * \text{Emp} \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [Q] \langle 0 \rangle & Q * R \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [Q * R] \langle 1 \rangle \end{array}$$

Inference rules for the cleaning \rightarrow judgment: $Q \rightarrow * R \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [P] \iff Q \rightarrow * R \dashv\vdash P$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{CLEAN}\rightarrow\text{-EMP-L} & \text{CLEAN}\rightarrow\text{-BASE} \\ \hline \text{Emp} \rightarrow * Q \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [Q] \langle 0 \rangle & Q \rightarrow * R \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [Q \rightarrow * R] \langle 1 \rangle \end{array}$$

Inference rules for the cleaning \forall judgment: $\forall x. Q \overset{\forall}{\rightsquigarrow} [R] \iff \forall x. Q \dashv\vdash R$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{CLEAN}\forall\text{-EMP} & \text{CLEAN}\forall\text{-BASE} \\ \frac{x \text{ inhabited}}{\forall x. \text{Emp} \overset{\forall}{\rightsquigarrow} [\text{Emp}]} \langle 0 \rangle & \frac{}{\forall x. Q \overset{\forall}{\rightsquigarrow} [\forall x. Q]} \langle 1 \rangle \end{array}$$

Inference rules for the cleaning \exists judgment: $\exists x. Q \overset{\exists}{\rightsquigarrow} [R] \iff \exists x. Q \dashv\vdash R$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{CLEAN}\exists\text{-EMP} & \text{CLEAN}\exists\text{-BASE} \\ \frac{x \text{ inhabited}}{\exists x. \text{Emp} \overset{\exists}{\rightsquigarrow} [\text{Emp}]} \langle 0 \rangle & \frac{}{\exists x. Q \overset{\exists}{\rightsquigarrow} [\exists x. Q]} \langle 1 \rangle \end{array}$$

Figure 4.8: Inference rules of the cleaning judgments

4.5 Cleaning up

At this step we have computed the simplified proposition $Kern_{Simp}$ and a context $\mathcal{C}_m\{\}$. As we have seen in examples such as those in Figures 4.6 and 4.7, the simplified term $Kern_{Simp}$ always contains a reducible Emp , which is created by an application of the terminal rule LINK-REFL .

In this section we further simplify the new goal proposition G_{Simp} in two different ways. We start by defining a new ‘cleaning’ judgment for each connective in Section 4.5.1. Then we use these judgments in Section 4.5.2 to simplify the term $Kern_{Simp}$ during the simplification of the kernel by adjusting the rules of the linking judgments. Finally in Section 4.5.3 we use these new cleaning judgments to add an extra cleanup judgment to simplify the new goal even further. In this last section we also give the final inference rule for linking, LINK-BACKWARD and LINK-FORWARD .

4.5.1 Cleaning Judgments for Most Connectives

In Figure 4.8 we define a cleaning judgment for most of the connectives in our logic. This figure displays both the semantics and the inference rules of these judgments. These judgments are heavily inspired by the ‘Make’ type classes from Krebbers et al. [2017], which we discuss in more depth in Section 5.2. Each of these judgments says that a term where the top-level connective is the judgments’ corresponding connective is equivalent to some simplified term.

Each of the judgments has a base case with the highest cost and at least one Emp case. The Emp cases are where the cleanup happens. Each application of an Emp rule removes the connective and possibly reduces the amount of Emp s. The base case never simplifies

or changes the propositions of the judgment. This is useful for terms that cannot be simplified, and for terms that we purposely leave as is, such as the quantifications that are not (necessarily) inhabited.

The **Emp** rules for the quantifications require that the quantifier is inhabited. This prevents information loss, as any time x is inhabited, both term $\forall x. \mathbf{Emp}$ and $\exists x. \mathbf{Emp}$ no longer provide the additional information that x is inhabited, since this is already known. Since the body is **Emp**, it also does not consume or provide any resources.

4.5.2 Adding Cleanup to the Rules for the Linking Judgments

We can use these cleaning judgments to modify the rules for the linking judgments so that each step cleans up after itself. Instead of providing all the modified rules, rules **LINK-RB*L-CLEAN** and **LINK-RB*V-CLEAN** show example modifications to the rules **LINK-RB*L** and **LINK-RB*V**, with the parts that are added or changed highlighted in red:

$$\frac{\text{LINK-RB*L-CLEAN} \quad [P] \vDash Q \multimap R_{\mathbb{L}} \quad P * R_{\mathbb{R}} \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [P']}{[P'] \vDash Q \multimap R_{\mathbb{L}} * R_{\mathbb{R}}} \quad \text{LINK-RB*V-CLEAN} \quad \frac{\forall x. [P] \vDash Q \multimap R \quad \forall x. P \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [P']}{[P'] \vDash Q \multimap \forall x. R}$$

These modifications will do more than removing the **Emp** generated by an application of **LINK-REFL**. It will clean up any occurrences of **Emp** that lies along either of the paths \vec{p}_l or \vec{p}_r . We do not consider this a problem, as it creates simpler terms that are equivalent. It does not, however, always clean up every occurrence of **Emp**. For example, a link of the propositions P in $(\mathbf{Emp} \multimap \mathbf{Emp}) \multimap P \multimap P$ results in $(\mathbf{Emp} \multimap \mathbf{Emp}) \multimap \mathbf{Emp}$, because the term $(\mathbf{Emp} \multimap \mathbf{Emp})$ is never traversed by the linking judgment, so therefore also not by the cleanup judgments. Additionally, this does not clean up any occurrences of **Emp** that are in the context function.

4.5.3 Cleanup Afterwards

Once we have found a simplified and cleaned term $Kern_{Simp}$ we might still want to do additional cleanup, if that term is **Emp** itself. Consider, for example, what should happen when we link the propositions P in $G = \mathbf{Emp} \multimap P \multimap P$. Without an additional cleanup step we would calculate $\mathcal{C}\{G\} = \mathbf{Emp} \multimap X$ and $Kern_{Simp} = \mathbf{Emp}$, which results in $G_{Simp} = \mathbf{Emp} \multimap \mathbf{Emp}$. Specifically, any time the result of simplifying the kernel is $Kern_{Simp} = \mathbf{Emp}$, we would like to clean it up. Luckily, we already have access to the path \vec{p}_c , so we know exact where the kernel, and therefore also the new **Emp**, is located.

We use another judgment for this task, one which only traverses the path \vec{p}_c and cleans up any **Emp**s along the way using the cleaning judgments. We use notation $Q \overset{\vec{p}_c}{\rightsquigarrow} [P]$, which is semantically equivalent to $Q \dashv\vdash P$ and is intended to be used on the already simplified term G_{Simp} .

The inference rules of this judgment should by now be straightforward, so instead of defining them all we give the example rule **CLEANUP*-R**:

$$\frac{\text{CLEANUP*-R} \quad R \overset{\vec{p}_c}{\rightsquigarrow} [R'] \quad Q * R' \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [QR']}{Q * R \overset{\mathbb{R}::\vec{p}_c}{\rightsquigarrow} [QR']}$$

We can use this final judgment to create the inference rules **LINK-BACKWARD** and **LINK-FORWARD**, which do linking with cleanup:

LINK-BACKWARD

$$\frac{G \stackrel{\vec{p}_c}{\models} [\mathcal{C}_{\rightarrow}\{Q \text{ -* } R\}] \quad [Kern_{Simp}] \models Q \text{ -* } R \quad \mathcal{C}_{\rightarrow}\{Kern_{Simp}\} \stackrel{\vec{p}_c}{\rightsquigarrow} [G_{Simp}] \quad \vdash G_{Simp}}{\vdash G}$$

LINK-FORWARD

$$\frac{G \stackrel{\vec{p}_c}{\models} [\mathcal{C}_{\leftarrow}\{Q * R\}] \quad Q * R \models [Kern_{Simp}] \quad \mathcal{C}_{\leftarrow}\{Kern_{Simp}\} \stackrel{\vec{p}_c}{\rightsquigarrow} [G_{Simp}] \quad \vdash G_{Simp}}{\vdash G}$$

Chapter 5

Implementation in Rocq

In this chapter we discuss how the `link` tactic is implemented in Rocq. Since the tactic makes extensive use of Rocq’s type class system, we start with a tutorial on these type classes in Section 5.1. Then, we show how to use existential variables and other tricks to enable a sort of logical programming with this system by giving implementations for the cleanup judgments from Section 4.5 in Section 5.2. Next, we discuss the implementation of the splitting judgment with a focus on the use of telescopes in Section 5.3. Finally, we discuss how to implement the two linking judgments with a single type class and how we use it to create the `link` tactic in Section 5.4.

5.1 Type Classes in a Nutshell

Our implementation makes extensive use of Rocq’s type class system [Sozeau and Oury, 2008]. In this subsection we will discuss what Rocq’s type classes are, from the perspective of a Haskell user. Rocq’s type classes are similar to Haskell’s type classes [Wadler and Blott, 1989] in that they can be used to mechanically build methods based on the type of the arguments. For Rocq, however, the methods that are part of the type class do not need to be computable functions, but could also be proof terms.

Let us consider the `Show` class from the type classes tutorial in software foundations [Foundations, 2025], which creates a pretty string from a value:

```
Class Show ( $\tau$  : Type) :=
{
  show :  $\tau$  → string
}.
```

It is possible to create instances for this class for both basic types, like `bool`, and parameterized types, like the Cartesian product $\tau_1 * \tau_2$:

```
Instance showBool : Show bool :=
{
  show b := if b then "true" else "false"
}.

Instance showPair '{! Show  $\tau_1$ , !Show  $\tau_2$ } : Show ( $\tau_1 * \tau_2$ ) :=
{
  show p :=
    let (t1,t2) := p in
    "(" ++ show t1 ++ " ," ++ show t2 ++ ")"
}.
```

The implicit arguments `Show τ_1` and `Show τ_2` are proof terms which say that the types τ_1 and τ_2 are also valid instances of `Show`. The `{!...}` notation tells Rocq to assume the provided free terms are implicit arguments, so there is a hidden assumption `{ τ_1 τ_2 : Type } in showPair`.

Let us consider what happens when we evaluate `show (true, false)`. First, Rocq verifies that the term is valid by checking if the type `(bool * bool)` is a valid instance of `Show`. Rocq sees that `showPair` instance matches the our type, if both sides of the product are valid instances. In this case, both sides of the product are of type `bool`, and there is an instance of `Show` for `bool` with no conditions, so therefore `bool` and by extension `(bool * bool)` are also a valid instances of `Show`. Next, the definitions of `showPair` and `showBool` can be used to evaluate the term `show (true, false)` to `"(true, false)"`. This example shows that adding an (implicit) argument of `Show τ` creates a hierarchical requirement. In this case, it requires that a value of type `Show ($\tau_1 * \tau_2$)` can only be an instance of `Show`, if both τ_1 and τ_2 are proven to be instances as well.

Since proofs and programs are fundamentally the same thing in Rocq, however, it is also possible to create a class with fields containing proof terms instead of, or in addition to, computable functions. Such proof terms in a type class are called *attributes*. The Rocq reference manual [Inria and contributors, 2024] gives the following example, which is such a combination of a computable function and an attribute:

```
Class EqDec ( $\tau$  : Type) :=
{
  eqb :  $\tau \rightarrow \tau \rightarrow \text{bool}$  ;
  eqb_leibniz :  $\forall x y, \text{eqb } x y = \text{true} \rightarrow x = y$ 
}.

```

Instances of this class need to provide a `bool` function that indicates equality, and a proof that if this function returns `true`, then the arguments are indeed equal. When creating such instances it is allowed to provide the proof term immediately, but if you prepend the instance definition with `#[refine]`, any remaining fields will have to be proven in proof mode. For example, one might create an instance of `EqDec` for `bool` like this:

```
#[refine] Instance eq_bool : EqDec bool :=
  { eqb x y := if x then y else negb y }.
Proof. (...) Defined.

```

5.2 Cleaning up with Type Class Inference

As one might expect of Rocq, the system to infer if the type of a value has a valid instance of a class is quite powerful. In this section we show how to use Rocq's type class inference to allow Rocq to automatically create proofs for the cleanup judgment $Q \xrightarrow{\vec{p}^c} [P]$ through the `MakeSimplified` type class. We start by introducing type classes for each of the cleanup judgments from Figure 4.8, which are all used by the `MakeSimplified` type class and later also by the `Link` type class. Additionally, during this section we will show some more techniques that make type class inference much more powerful: using class arguments as output and adding external hints, costs, and phantom arguments.

Class Arguments as Output If an argument of a type class is an *existential variable* (evar), then the type class system will attempt to infer what the value of this evar should be to create a valid instance. We can think of this inference as an alternative way to let

type class inference create output. For the type class implementations of the cleanup judgments from Section 4.5 we want to leverage this functionality to let Rocq calculate automatically what the value of the output between the double square braces is. Consider the type class `MakeSep Q R QR` originally made for `iFrame` [Krebbers et al., 2017], which implements the judgment $Q * R \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [QR]$:

```

Class MakeSep Q R QR := { makeSep: Q * R -| 1| QR }.
Global Hint Mode MakeSep ! ! - : type class_instances.

Global Instance makeSep_l_true R : MakeSep emp R R | 0.
Proof. (...)

Global Instance makeSep_r_true Q : MakeSep Q emp Q | 0.
Proof. (...)

Global Instance makeSep_default Q R : MakeSep Q R (Q * R) | 1.
Proof. (...)

```

The `Hint Mode` command specifies which of the arguments of `MakeSep` are allowed to be, or contain, evars. An exclamation mark means that the argument at that position is allowed to contain evars, but not be an evar itself, and a dash means that it is allowed to be evars as well. Later in this paper we will also see the use of a `+` symbol, which indicates the value can neither be, nor contain, an evar. The hint for `MakeSep` therefore specifies that the terms `Q` and `R` must be provided, so they are input, and that the term `QR` can be an evar, so it is considered output.

Adding Costs to Instances The instances of the `MakeSep` type class are all followed by a number after a vertical line, like `| 1`. This number indicates a cost, which directs type class inference in a similar way to described in Section 4.2. For example, a term `MakeSep P emp ?Q` has two possible valid terms for the evar `?Q`; `P` and `P * emp`. However, since `makeSep_r_true` has a lower cost, `P` without the `Emp` is the one that will be picked when using the type class system to infer the value of `?Q`.

Adding External Hints to the Inhabited Type Class We create matching type classes for each of the cleanup judgments described in Section 4.5. The wand cleanup class can be implemented in a way similar to the `makeSep` type class above. The classes for the quantifiers, however, need to implement a way to automatically derive if the quantifier x is inhabited. Luckily, the `coq-std++` library (`stdpp`) [std++ team, 2025] provides the `Inhabited` type class:

```

Class Inhabited (A : Type) : Type := populate { inhabitant : A }.

```

The `Inhabited` type class simply asserts that a type A is inhabited with a witness called `inhabitant`. The library provides instances for various well-known basic and composite types, such as booleans, lists, and the Cartesian product:

```

Global Instance bool_inhabited : Inhabited bool := populate true.

Global Instance list_inhabited {A} : Inhabited (list A) := populate [].

Global Instance prod_inhabited {A B} (iA : Inhabited A)
  (iB : Inhabited B) : Inhabited (A * B) := (...)

```

A type class search for `Inhabited τ` does not, however, prove automatically that a type is inhabited if we have an instance of τ in the context. For our use case this is one of the more important requirements, as we often use generic types and add instances

of that type to the context. Instead of using standard type class instances to fix this problem, we use an *external hint*. Just like an instance, an external hint is applied for a specific syntax, and with a provided cost. Unlike an instance, however, an external hint is a tactic that should be applied when the requirements are met. We add the following external hint:

```
Global Hint Extern 1 (Inhabited _) =>
  split; assumption : typeclass_instances.
```

This says that if type class search has to prove a term `Inhabited _`, where `_` can be any term, then it should apply the tactic `split; assumption`. The `split` tactic is used to strip away the encapsulation of the `Inhabited` class, and the `assumption` tactic is then used to search for a witness in the context. It should do this with a cost of one.

This way, if there is an inhabitant $t_1 : \tau_1$ and an inhabitant $t_2 : \tau_2$ in our context, `Inhabited ($\tau_1 * \tau_2$)` will succeed with an application of type class search, because the `prod_inhabited` instance recursively requires `Inhabited τ_1` and `Inhabited τ_2` , which are both found by our external hint.

We have not, however, set up the system to do the reverse: If there is a witness $t : \tau_1 \times \tau_2$, then `Inhabited τ_1` will not succeed automatically with type class search. This is a problem we do not solve in this thesis.

Directing the final cleanup judgment with Phantom Arguments Now that we have all the cleaning type classes for the connectives, we can use them for the cleanup step at the end of the linking process. We finally create the type class `MakeSimplified`, which corresponds to the judgment $Q \xrightarrow{\vec{p}_c} [P]$:

```
Class MakeSimplified pc Q P := { isSimple: Q -| P }.
Global Hint Mode Make ! ! - : typeclass_instances.
```

The argument `pc` is a *phantom argument*. It has no semantic meaning, but will be used to direct and limit the type class inference. The instances for this class are a straightforward translation from the rules of the cleanup judgment. Since we only explicitly provided the rule `CLEANUP*- \mathbb{R}` for this judgment, we do the same for the instance:

```
Global Instance makeSimplified_sep_r pc Q R R' QR' :
  MakeSimplified pc R R' →
  MakeSep Q R' QR' →
  MakeSimplified (Right :: pc) (Q * R) PR'.
Proof. (...)
```

Notice that since in the conclusion of this instance the path has to start with an \mathbb{R} , this restricts inference to only simplify below the proposition R . We require similar restrictions for the other instances. The phantom argument `pc` therefore restricts the type class inference, requiring that the judgment cleans up only the part of the proposition that come in contact with the path \vec{p}_c .

Using the Type Class to Create a Tactic We can now use the `MakeSimplified` type class to create a lemma and a tactic that uses this type class. Consider the following lemma:

```
Lemma use_simplifier {P PSimplified} p :
  MakePathSimplified p P PSimplified →
  (|- PSimplified) →
  |- P.
Proof.
```

We can use `eapply` with a given path to let Rocq create evars for the unknown values. This application leads creates two new goals: `MakePathSimplified \vec{p}_c G PSimplified` and `⊢ PSimplified`. The first new goal can be solved with type inference by calling `apply _` or `stdpp`'s `tc_solve` (which is often subtly better). Our next goal becomes `⊢ PSimplified`, where type class inference gave a value to `PSimplified`. We can create a tactic that does this in one go:

```
Tactic Notation "simplify_no_ipm" open_constr(path) :=
  eapply (use_simplifier path); [ tc_solve | ].
```

We call this tactic `simplify_no_ipm` because it does not interact well with Iris Proof Mode yet. Making it suitable for Iris Proof Mode is not hard, but does require some technical knowledge of the inner workings of the Iris Proof Mode which we do not explain in this thesis.

5.3 Splitting the Context with Telescopes

This section describes the type class `Split`, which is an implementation of the judgment $Q \stackrel{\vec{p}_c}{\models} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]$ described in Section 4.3, with a focus on the use of telescopes to address the splitting with quantifiers issue discussed in that section. Throughout this and the following sections we implicitly assume the following types unless otherwise specified, and add `PROP` to the global context as the type of generic propositions of BI (*Prop*):

```
Section Split_Context.
Context { PROP : bi }.
Implicit Types P Q R : PROP. (* Propositions in BI *)
Implicit Types TT : tele. (* telescopes *)
Implicit Types τ : Type. (* generic types *)
Implicit Types m : bool. (* a boolean to indicate monotonicity *)
Implicit Types pc pl pr : Path. (* paths as lists of directions *)
...

```

In order to implement the splitting judgment $Q \stackrel{\vec{p}_c}{\models} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]$ in Rocq, we need to resolve the simplification concerning quantifiers described in Section 4.3, which is that the kernel P should somehow be able to bind quantifiers. Consider, for example, what should happen when we try to split using the path $\vec{p}_c = [\mathbb{R}]$ from the proposition

$$G \triangleq \forall x : \tau. F x \multimap \forall y : T x. G x y \multimap H x y$$

Upon inspection, we see that the kernel $Kern$ and context $\mathcal{C}\{\}$ should be the following respective functions:

$$Kern \triangleq \lambda(x : \tau) (y : T x). G x y \multimap H x y \tag{5.1}$$

$$\mathcal{C}\{\} \triangleq \lambda(X : \forall x : \tau. T x \rightarrow Prop). \forall x : \tau. F x \multimap \forall y : T x. X x y \tag{5.2}$$

Clearly, this requires that the kernel is not just a proposition in separation logic, but a function with some number of dependently typed arguments to propositions instead. Similarly, the argument of our context functions must of the same types. We create the `Split` type class, which represents the splitting judgment $Q \stackrel{\vec{p}_c}{\models} [\mathcal{C}_m\{P\}]$, and adapt it to use a data type called *telescopes* (TT) and their function-like type $TT \xrightarrow{t} \tau$, which represents telescopic functions:

```

Class Split TT Q pc (C : (TT -t> PROP) → PROP) (P : TT -t> PROP) m := {
  getContext : Q -|- C P;
  isMonoContext : if m then Monotone C else Antimonotone C
}.
Global Hint Mode Split - ! ! - - - : typeclass_instances.

Notation "Q '≡pc' '[[ ' C ' @ ' P ' ]]' ' m" := (Split _ Q pc C P m)
(format "Q ≡pc { C @ P } m", at level 99).

```

Compared to the judgment, the type class takes an additional argument TT , which is the type of the telescope. This telescope represents the type of the arguments of the function P , so the adapted judgment/type class is parameterized over the types of the arguments of P .

Since the type of the context function has changed, our definitions of monotonicity Equations (4.1) and (4.2) have to be adapted for this new type as well. The notation ‘ $\forall..y$ ’ should be read as a telescopic universal quantification and will be further explained in the next paragraph:

```

Definition Monotone { TT } (C : (TT -t> PROP) → PROP) :=
  ∀ (P Q : TT -t> PROP), (∀ .. y , tele_app P y ⊢ tele_app Q y) →
  C P ⊢ C Q.

```

```

Definition Antimonotone { TT } (C : (TT -t> PROP) → PROP) :=
  ∀ (P Q : TT -t> PROP), (∀ .. y , tele_app Q y ⊢ tele_app P y) →
  C P ⊢ C Q.

```

Telescopes What are these telescopes, telescopic functions and quantifications? Telescopes are an idea from typed lambda calculus from de Bruijn [1991], where it was notation for a list of substitutions. In Rocq, telescopes are a tool to represent some amount of (dependent) function arguments with a single value. In our implementation we use the formalization and implementation provided by the stdpp library [std++ team, 2025].

Telescopes are an inductively defined structure of arguments, which behaves similar to a list of values of possibly dependent types if they are applied to the custom function type made for these telescopes, $f : TT \xrightarrow{t} \tau$:

```

Inductive tele : Type :=
| Tele0 : tele
| TeleS {X} (binder : X → tele) : tele.

Notation "'[tele' x .. z ]'" :=
  (TeleS (fun x => .. (TeleS (fun z => Tele0)) ..))
  (x binder, z binder, format "[tele '[hv' x .. z ]']").

Fixpoint tele_fun (TT : tele) (τ : Type) : Type :=
  match TT with
  | Tele0 => τ
  | TeleS b => ∀ x, tele_fun (b x) τ
  end.

Notation "TT -t> τ" :=
  (tele_fun TT τ) (at level 99, A at level 200, right associativity).

```

This custom function type represents an uncurried n-ary function. If we provide it a telescope value, this function type unrolls the telescope to create a standard Rocq

function that applies the arguments of the telescope one-by-one. We therefore see that this simplifies to standard Rocq functions:

```

Definition nat_argument := [tele (y : nat)].
Definition nat_bool_arguments := [tele (v: nat) (w: bool)].
Definition no_arguments := [tele].

Check ((λ x : nat, x) : nat_argument -t> nat).
Check ((λ (x: nat) (b: bool), x) : nat_bool_arguments -t> nat).
Check (4 : no_arguments -t> nat).

```

Similarly, we see that the example context from Equation (5.2) can be rewritten with telescopes:

$$\mathcal{C}\{\} = \lambda(X : [tele (x : \tau)(y : Tx)] \xrightarrow{t} Prop). \forall x : \tau. F x \text{ -* } \forall y : Tx. X x y$$

We can also define a folding function `tele_fold` that uses these telescopic functions to create telescopic quantification. Telescopic quantification should be seen as a (dependent) list of quantifications of the types in the telescope.

```

Definition tele_fold {X Y} {TT : tele} (step : ∀ {τ : Type}, (τ → Y) → Y)
  (base : X → Y) : (TT -t> X) → Y :=
  (fix rec {TT} : (TT -t> X) → Y :=
    match TT as TT return (TT -t> X) → Y with
    | Tele0 => λ x : X, base x
    | TeleS b => λ f, step (λ x, rec (f x))
  end) TT.

Definition tforall {TT : tele} (Ψ : TT → Prop) : Prop :=
  tele_fold (λ (τ : Type) (b : τ → Prop), ∀ x : T, b x) (λ x, x) (tele_bind Ψ).
Global Arguments tforall {!_} _ /.

Definition texist {TT : tele} (Ψ : TT → Prop) : Prop :=
  tele_fold ex (λ x, x) (tele_bind Ψ).
Global Arguments texist {!_} _ /.

Notation "'∀ ..' x .. y , P" := (tforall (λ x, .. (tforall (λ y, P)) .. ))
  (at level 200, x binder, y binder, right associativity,
  format "∀ .. x .. y , P") : stdpp_scope.
Notation "'∃ ..' x .. y , P" := (texist (λ x, .. (texist (λ y, P)) .. ))
  (at level 200, x binder, y binder, right associativity,
  format "∃ .. x .. y , P") : stdpp_scope.

```

Instances of the Split type class Most of the non-quantification instances of the `Split` type class somewhat ignore the fact that telescopes are used. For all of these instances, the types of the telescopes do not change after an application of these instances. The implementations of these rules are therefore all very straightforward, especially when comparing them to the rules of the judgment given in Figure 4.1. Because of this, we only show the instance that corresponds to the ruled `SPLIT-*L`:

```

Global Instance split_wand_l {TT} Q R pc (C : (TT -t> PROP) → PROP)
  (P : TT -t> PROP) m :
  Q =|~{ pc } [[ C @ P ] m →
  (Q -* R) =|~{ Left :: pc } [[ λ X, (C X -* R)%I @ P ] (negb m) | 0.
Proof. (...)

```

The scope specifier `%I` is required in the function because Rocq would otherwise assume the wrong scope and is unable to infer it automatically.

The instances of the quantifiers are a bit more interesting, since they manipulate the telescopes. The following instance is an implementation of the rule `SPLIT \forall` :

```
Global Instance split_forall { $\tau$ } {MakeTT :  $\tau \rightarrow \text{tele}$ } (Q :  $\tau \rightarrow \text{PROP}$ ) cp
  (C :  $\forall x, (\text{MakeTT } x \text{ -t> PROP}) \rightarrow \text{PROP}$ ) (P :  $\forall x, \text{MakeTT } x \text{ -t> PROP}$ ) m :
  ( $\forall x, \text{Split } (\text{MakeTT } x) (Q x) \text{ cp } (C x) (P x) m$ )  $\rightarrow$ 
  Split (TeleS MakeTT) ( $\forall x, Q x$ ) cp ( $\lambda X, \forall x, C x (X x)$ )%I P m | 0.
Proof. (...)
```

Here we can see exactly how the quantifiers are manipulated. We want to add the quantifier $x : \tau$ from the the telescope of antecedent to the telescope of the precedent. We do this by taking a function `MakeTT` : $\tau \rightarrow \text{tele}$ as an argument of the instance, which creates the telescope of the precedent when given a value of type τ . Additionally, the function type of `MakeTT` fits exactly as an argument for the successor telescope constructor `TeleS`, which creates the larger telescope with τ as the first argument.

We can now create an intermediate lemma that splits the context, which we use later on in the definition of the `link` tactic:

```
Lemma use_context { TT } pc Q (C : (TT -t> PROP)  $\rightarrow$  PROP) (P : (TT -t> PROP)) m :
  Q  $\models$  { pc } [ C @ P ] m  $\rightarrow$ 
  (if m then Monotone C else Antimonotone C)  $\rightarrow$   $\vdash$  C P  $\rightarrow$ 
   $\vdash$  Q.
Proof. (...)
```

5.4 The Link Type Class and the Final Tactic

We implement both linking judgments in a single class, by adding a boolean flag that determines whether the judgment is a forward or backward link:

```
Class Link (isBackward : bool) lp rp P Q R := {
  isLink: if isBackward then P  $\vdash$  Q  $\ast$  R else Q  $\ast$  R  $\vdash$  P
}.
Global Hint Mode Link ! - - - ! ! : typeclass_instances.

Notation "'[[ ' P ']]'  $\models$  {' pl ';' pr '}' Q  $\ast$  R" := (Link true pl pr P Q R)
  (format "[[ P ]]  $\models$  { pl ; pr } Q  $\ast$  R", at level 99).

Notation "Q  $\ast$  R  $\models$  {' pl ';' pr '}' '[[ ' P ']]'" := (Link false pl pr P Q R)
  (format "Q  $\ast$  R  $\models$  { pl ; pr } [[ P ]]", at level 99).
```

Once again, most of the non-QU instances of our `link` type class are very straightforward translations of the inference rules shown in Figures 4.3 and 4.4. We therefore only present the implementations of `LINK-RB \ast R`, `LINK-LF \ast L` and `LINK-LB \exists` , including cleanup described in Figure 4.8:

```
Lemma link_rb_sep_R P lp rp Q RL RR RLP :
  [[ P ]]  $\models$  {lp; rp} Q  $\ast$  RR  $\rightarrow$ 
  MakeSep RL P RLP  $\rightarrow$ 
  [[ RLP ]]  $\models$  {lp; Right :: rp} Q  $\ast$  R1  $\ast$  RR.
Proof. (...)
```

```
Lemma link_lf_wand_L QL QR R lp rp P PtoQR :
  [[ P ]]  $\models$  {rp; lp} R  $\ast$  QL  $\rightarrow$ 
  MakeWand P QR PtoQR  $\rightarrow$ 
  (QL  $\ast$  QR)  $\ast$  R  $\models$  {Left :: lp ; rp} [[ PtoQR ]].
Proof. (...)
```

```

Lemma link_lb_exists { $\tau$ } (P :  $\tau \rightarrow$  PROP) lp rp (Q :  $\tau \rightarrow$  PROP) R PAll:
  ( $\forall$  x,  $\llbracket$  P x  $\rrbracket$   $\models$ {lp; rp} (Q x)  $=*$  R)  $\rightarrow$ 
  MakeAll P PAll  $\rightarrow$ 
   $\llbracket$  PAll  $\rrbracket$   $\models$ {lp; rp}  $\exists$  x, Q x  $=*$  R.
Proof. (...)

```

Quantifying the Uninstantiated The instances that correspond to the QU rules are a bit more involved. Consider a possible implementation of LINK-LB \forall -QU

```

Lemma link_lb_forall_qu_v1 { $\tau$  TT} (P : TT  $\rightarrow$  PROP) lp rp (Q :  $\tau \rightarrow$  PROP) R
  (f: TT  $\rightarrow$   $\tau$ ):
  ( $\forall$  (tt : TT),  $\llbracket$  P tt  $\rrbracket$   $\models$ {lp; rp} (Q (f tt))  $=*$  R)  $\rightarrow$ 
   $\llbracket$   $\exists$  .. tt, P tt  $\rrbracket$   $\models$ {lp; rp} ( $\forall$  x, Q x)  $=*$  R.
Proof. (...)

```

This is a sound instance that matches the rule, but there are a few problems that need to be addressed before it is a usable instance for type class search. The way this rule is set up, Rocq cannot infer the values of P and f automatically. To solve this, QU introduces new evars $P' : Prop$ and $x : \tau$ and add the requirements that $P' = P \text{ tt}$ and $x = f \text{ tt}$, which can be inferred using the type class system. Once these values are inferred, QU uses some clever tricks and tactics to calculate what the values of f and P should be. For a thorough explanation of how these values are calculated and how telescopes are involved we defer to Mulder and Krebbers [2024]. The final implementation becomes the following:

```

Lemma link_lb_forall_qu { $\tau$  TT} (P : TT  $\rightarrow$  PROP) lp rp (Q :  $\tau \rightarrow$  PROP) R
  (f: TT  $\rightarrow$   $\tau$ ):
  ( $\forall$  (tt : TT),
     $\exists$  P' x,
    ( $\llbracket$  P'  $\rrbracket$   $\models$ {lp; rp} (Q x)  $=*$  R)  $\wedge$ 
    GatherEvarsEq x (f tt)  $\wedge$ 
    TCEq P' (P tt)
  )  $\rightarrow$ 
   $\llbracket$   $\exists$  .. tt, P tt  $\rrbracket$   $\models$ {lp; rp} ( $\forall$  x, Q x)  $=*$  R.

```

Here `GatherEvarsEq` is another type class that calculates what the value of f is using the crucial `solve.evar.tele.equality` tactic described by QU. The `TCEq` type class is a helper type class from `stdpp`, which calculates the value of P with a simple call to the `reflexivity` tactic. The instance in this shape still cannot be solved by type class inference, however, as existential variables will not be created in such an instance, so we need to use an external hint which creates the evars for this instance, or we could use another dedicated type class which contains only the conditions for this type class.

Final Lemma and link Tactic Now that we have implemented all the judgments as type classes, we can create another lemma and finally the `link` tactic. We have a lemma for both backward and forward links:

```

Lemma apply_link_backward { P Q R } lp rp :
   $\llbracket$  P  $\rrbracket$   $\models$ {lp; rp} Q  $=*$  R  $\rightarrow$ 
  P  $\vdash$  (Q  $*$  R).
Proof. (...)

Lemma apply_link_forward { P Q R } lp rp :
  Q  $*$  R  $\models$ {lp; rp}  $\llbracket$  P  $\rrbracket$   $\rightarrow$ 
  (Q  $*$  R)  $\vdash$  P.
Proof. (...)

```

We can use these lemmas and combine them with the lemmas and tactics mentioned previously to create the tactic `link_no_pm`:

```
(* simplifies telescopes, and tries to do no more than that *)
Ltac simplify_telescope :=
  cbv beta iota delta
    [ tele_app tforall texist tele_fold tele_bind tele_fun tele_arg_head ].

Tactic Notation "link_no_pm" open_constr(p) open_constr(lp) open_constr(rp) :=
(* Split the context based on path p or fail with custom message *)
first
  [ notypeclasses refine (use_context p _ _ _ _ _); [ tc_solve | ]
  | fail 1 "Failed to find context" ];
(* introduce the monotonicity calculated by Split *)
intros _HCPol;
lazymatch goal with
| |- ⊢ ( _ ?G) ⇒ eapply bi_trans;
  (* apply (anti)monotonicity, so we can simplify under the context *)
  [ eapply (_HCPol _ G);
    simplify_telescope;
    intros;
    (* search for backward or forward links with given paths lp rp *)
    first
      [ notypeclasses refine (apply_link_backward lp rp _); tc_solve
      | notypeclasses refine (apply_link_forward lp rp _); tc_solve
      | fail 1 "Failed to find link" ]
  | ]
end;
(* fill in the simplified kernel in the context function *)
unfold id;
cbv beta;
(* remove the monotonicity hypothesis from the context *)
clear _HCPol;
(* Apply final simplification based on p *)
simplify_no_pm p

Tactic Notation "link" open_constr(lp) open_constr(rp) :=
  link [] lp rp.

Tactic Notation "link" open_constr(p) :=
  link p _ _ .

Tactic Notation "link" :=
  link [] _ _ .
```

In order to use the tactic in IPM, some small changes to the lemmas and tactics should be made which we will not explain. The implementations of `link.to` and `link.hyps` are much simpler, since they require neither the splitting the context step, nor the final cleanup step, and we also already know whether the link is forwards or backwards. Since they also require the technical knowledge about IPM, however, we will give their definition either.

Chapter 6

Related Work

This chapter examines how our `link` tactic relates to existing work in subformula linking and Rocq tactics. In Section 6.1 we discuss the theoretical foundations, from examining early approaches like Proof by Pointing to newer systems like Proffnt and Actema. In Section 6.2 we compare our approach with practical implementations in separation logic, particularly Iris’s `iFrame` tactic and generalized rewriting techniques.

6.1 Subformula Linking

This section relates the `link` tactic to its foundations from subformula linking. As we discussed before in the introduction, these systems use various logics, like linear or first-order intuitionistic logic. Sometimes using a different logic necessarily results in different rules to maintain soundness of the rules, and sometimes the structure of the rules can be mostly preserved when translating it to separation logic yet our implementation differs none the less. In this section we highlight some of both cases by discussing each of the mentioned systems in the introduction.

6.1.1 Proof by Pointing

The original Proof by Pointing paper [Bertot et al., 1994] describes derivation rules for a few different logics, both intuitionistic and classical, but not substructural. Unlike our system, Proof by Pointing describes a process of selecting a *single* subformula, and such an interaction will either *dismiss* the goal entirely or create *some amount* of new goals. For example, if we select the first P in $Q \vdash (\underline{P} \rightarrow P) \wedge Q$, the system generates the new goals: $Q \vdash Q$. However, if we select the first P in $Q \vdash (\underline{P} \rightarrow P \wedge Q) \wedge Q$, the system generates two new goals: $P, Q \vdash P \wedge Q$ and $Q \vdash Q$.

When selecting a nested subformula with Proof by Pointing, the selected subformula is brought to the top by a process it calls ‘selection propagation’. Once the selected subformula is at top-level, the system attempts to resolve the goal essentially with an application of the `assumption` tactic from Rocq. We highlight the rules $\wedge\text{RIGHT}_1$ and $\rightarrow\text{RIGHT}_1$ which are used for the partial derivations of the examples, which are shown in Figures 6.1 and 6.2:

$$\begin{array}{c} \wedge\text{RIGHT}_1 \\ \frac{\Gamma \vdash \boxed{P} \quad \Gamma \vdash Q}{\Gamma \vdash \boxed{P} \wedge Q} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \rightarrow\text{RIGHT}_1 \\ \frac{\boxed{A}, \Gamma \vdash B}{\Gamma \vdash \boxed{A} \rightarrow B} \end{array}$$

At each application of a rule, the box indicates which proposition *contains* the selected subformula, so it is not a judgment in the way we have used them in this paper.

$$\frac{\frac{\overline{P, Q \vdash P} \text{ ASSUMPTION}}{Q \vdash \underline{P} \rightarrow P} \rightarrow\text{RIGHT}_1 \quad Q \vdash Q}{Q \vdash (\underline{P} \rightarrow P) \wedge Q} \wedge\text{RIGHT}_1$$

Figure 6.1: Example of partial derivations generated by selecting the first P in $Q \vdash (\underline{P} \rightarrow P) \wedge Q$. The selected \underline{P} can be resolved with an assumption once it is at top-level, so the only new goal is $Q \vdash Q$.

$$\frac{\frac{\underline{P}, Q \vdash P \wedge Q}{Q \vdash \underline{P} \rightarrow P \wedge Q} \rightarrow\text{RIGHT}_1 \quad Q \vdash Q}{Q \vdash (\underline{P} \rightarrow P \wedge Q) \wedge Q} \wedge\text{RIGHT}_1$$

Figure 6.2: Example of partial derivations generated by selecting the first P in $Q \vdash (\underline{P} \rightarrow P \wedge Q) \wedge Q$. The selected \underline{P} cannot be resolved with an assumption, so multiple new goals are created.

6.1.2 Dealing with Depth

In this subsection we compare how previous subformula linking systems have resolved the challenge of linking subformula at arbitrary depth. We do so for the systems *Profound*, *ProfInt* and *Actema*.

The first paper to introduce subformula linking did so in linear logic with *Profound* [Chaudhuri, 2013], and is very similar in many aspects to the later *ProfInt* system [Chaudhuri, 2021], which is effectively **Profound** for **Intuitionistic** logic. Both of these systems are specialized proof assistants which require the user to drag one subformula to another as the only interaction.

These systems also share a lot of theoretical foundations. For example, both systems replace the least common ancestor connective of the linking terms. A difference that arises from the logic, however, is that in *Profound* there is a single new connective while *ProfInt* requires two, like we have as well. *ProfInt* also has two different types of context, monotone and antimonotone, while the *Profound* system makes no such distinction.

The interaction rules for the new connective(s), however, are structurally different from the judgments we use in our thesis. Unlike the rules for our judgments, the rules for *ProfInt*'s connectives are all under arbitrary monotone or antimonotone context. Additionally, the context to reach the special connective changes after each application. See, for example, the rule $\blacktriangleright \wedge_1$:

$$\frac{\blacktriangleright \wedge_1 \quad \mathcal{C}\{(P \blacktriangleright Q) \wedge R\}}{\mathcal{C}\{P \blacktriangleright (Q \wedge R)\}}$$

In this rule, the new connective is at top-level under the context in the conclusion of the rule, but not in the antecedent. If we want to apply another rule at the next step, we therefore need to consider a new context, where the conjunction and R have to be added.

ProfInt is capable of translating a derivation to *Rocq*. In contrast to our type class inference for an entire interaction which requires no transitivity at intermediate steps, each application of an interaction rule is passed to a list of transitivity rules which ensure the rule is applied to the right subformula.

The *Actema* system by Donato et al. [2022] is slightly different. Just like *ProfInt*, *Actema* is a proof assistant for intuitionistic logic, which requires drag-and-drop as the main interaction. Unlike *ProfInt*, however, it does not allow dragging arbitrary subformula to others. In stead, it provides a context Γ , which can be added to by double

clicking on subformulas that are in front of an arrow. Once there are propositions in this context, they can be dragged on either other propositions in the context to create a forward link, or on the goal for a backward link. It also provides other interactions, such as eliminating propositions in the context or even a new type of link, the rewrite link, where if one of the propositions is an equality, and the other proposition will be rewritten using this equality.

Since links in Actema can only be made between propositions in a context and other propositions that are either in the context or are the goal, part of the problem of depth has been simplified. In our system, this would be very similar to using IPM to introduce propositions, and then only using the `link_to` tactic for backward goals and `link_hyps` for backward goals, see Section 3.6. $\Gamma \vdash P$ between subformula in different propositions in the context Γ , or between subformula of a proposition in the context and the goal, though it also allows a different type of link for rewriting equalities. This is future work for our system.

The inference rules for simplifying the kernel are similar to ProfInt, in that the context at which the rules should be applied changes at each step.

6.1.3 Navigating Non-determinism

In Section 4.4.4 we discussed the non-determinism of the rules, where particularly critical pairs of rules where the application order matters were the most difficult to solve. All of the intuitionistic systems described so far, ProfInt, Actema and simple QU Mulder and Krebbers [2024], have a single, but different, critical pair from our system. In this subsection we describe why the critical pair is a different pair of rules and compare how these systems deal with this problem.

The left backward rules for conjunction (rules $L \wedge L$ and $L \wedge R$) of these systems have a fundamentally different shape from our rules $LINK-LB*L$ and $LINK-LB*R$. The rule shown here is translated to the typeclass-like notation we have used for this paper, with the main difference that the \blacktriangleright replaces a single occurrence of \rightarrow in a proposition, similar to how the $\rightarrow*$ replaces a single occurrence \rightarrow in our system.

$$\frac{L \wedge L \quad [P] \vDash Q_L \blacktriangleright R}{[P] \vDash Q_L \wedge Q_R \blacktriangleright R} \qquad \frac{L \wedge R \quad [P] \vDash Q_R \blacktriangleright R}{[P] \vDash Q_L \wedge Q_R \blacktriangleright R}$$

Sadly, we cannot reduce the number of critical pairs by translating these rules to BI, as these rules are not sound in our logic. This is because the not selected resource would be dropped, so we would need to use weakening. Even if we had access to weakening by using an affine BI, however, matching the shape of this rule is still not desirable. Consider, for example, the proposition $P * Q \rightarrow* Q * P$. After linking the propositions P , we would be left with a goal $\text{Emp} \vdash Q$. Since we have no access to contraction, this goal therefore becomes unprovable in an affine logic that uses this rule shape.

None of the other differences in the rules change the number of critical pairs compared to the other intuitionistic systems. The only critical pairs in those systems occur when combining the forward disjunction and forward implication rules. This critical pair is not present in our system because we do not define rules for disjunction. The Profound system has a different critical pair: an interaction with two \exists -formulas.

Unlike our system, Actema and QU, the systems Profound and ProfInt do not only use heuristics to resolve these critical pairs. Instead, they add additional information to a link, where one of the linking terms is labeled a ‘source’ and the other a ‘sink’ in Profound or ‘destination’ in ProfInt, based on the direction of the drag-and-drop interaction. This label is then used to prioritize which of the rules of a critical pair should be applied first. Adding this idea could be a should be explored in later iterations of the tactic. This

could, for example, be achieved by adding an additional boolean argument `leftIsSink` to the type class, which is then used to create 2 variants for the rules of the critical pairs. For example, the implementation for the rule `LINK-LB*L` could become the following:

```
Global Instance link_lb_sep_L_leftIsSink P lp rp Q1 Q2 R Q2toP:
  Link true lp; rp P Q1 R true →
  MakeWand Q2 P Q2toP →
  Link true (Left :: lp) rp Q2toP (Q1 * Q2) R true | 9.
Proof. (...)

Global Instance link_lb_sep_L_rightIsSink P lp rp Q1 Q2 R Q2toP:
  Link true lp; rp P Q1 R false →
  MakeWand Q2 P Q2toP →
  Link true (Left :: lp) rp Q2toP (Q1 * Q2) R false | 11.
Proof. (...)
```

We predict that this would add more power to the user by making it easier to link specific propositions without creating an unprovable goal, but would not affect the provability of a goal over all, as a provable goal in the current implementation should always contain a pair of links that do not affect the provability.

6.2 Separation Logic and Rocq

In this section we explore some tools developed for separation logic or Rocq that use similar ideas to those presented in this thesis. In Section 6.2.1 we show how the `iFrame` tactic is very closely related to `link`. Next, in Section 6.2.2 we discuss how `Diaframe` uses Quantifying the Uninstantiated. Finally, in Section 6.2.3 we describe a different way to rewrite under contexts and why we do not use these techniques.

6.2.1 Iris' iFrame

We discussed some of the basics of Iris Proof Mode [Krebbers et al., 2017] in Section 2.4. We mentioned how the `iFrame` tactic is capable of cancelling propositions, similar to `link`. The implementation of `iFrame` uses type classes similar to our tactic. The main type class it tries to instantiate is the `Frame` type class:

```
Class Frame {PROP : bi} (p : bool) (R P Q : PROP) := frame : □?p R * Q ⊢ P.
Global Hint Mode Frame + + ! ! - : typeclass_instances.

(* Our type class, for reference *)
Class Link (isBackward : bool) p1 pr P Q R := {
  isLink: if isBackward then P ⊢ Q -* R else Q * R ⊢ P
}.
Global Hint Mode Link ! - - - ! ! : typeclass_instances.
```

There are two main differences with our `Link` class. The `Frame` class is also capable of cancelling terms in the persistent context where propositions are copyable, which is what the `□?p` notation indicates. Additionally, the class only allows backward links. The type classes are essentially the same if the arguments `p` from `Frame` and `isBackward` from `Link` are both `false`. The aim of the tactic is to be used in conjunction with the rest of the Iris system. It therefore chooses not to perform some steps which it could perform based on this definition of the type class, but are handled by different tactics, favoring a speedy implementation instead. We highlight a few of the differences:

Deeper and Forward Links: The `iFrame` tactic will only link propositions from the spatial (and possibly persistent) context and is mostly aimed for linking top-level propositions from the context to deeper propositions in the goal. For example, while the `iFrame` tactic is capable of cancelling the propositions P and Q when the context contains these propositions separately in the following proof state:

```
(* "HP": P *)
(* "HQ": Q *)
(* -----* *)
(* P * Q *)
iFrame
(* All goals completed. *)
```

It will fail to cancel either if they are nested in a conjunction that does not exactly match the hypothesis:

```
(* "HP": P * Q *)
(* -----* *)
(* Q * P *)
iFrame
(* "HP": P * Q *)
(* -----* *)
(* Q * P *)
```

The Iris user is expected to first eliminate such a hypothesis $P * Q$ into $H_1 : P$ and $H_2 : Q$ using the `iDestruct` tactic. Not all propositions can be destructed with introduction patterns, however, like propositions containing wands. For example, the proposition $P \multimap (P \multimap \exists x. Q x) \multimap \exists x. Q x$ will need to use an application of a tactic like `iSpecialize` in addition to `iIntros` and framing.

```
(* "HP" : P *)
(* "H" : P \multimap \exists x : \tau, Q x *)
(* -----* *)
(* \exists x : \tau, Q x *)
iFrame
(* No changes to the state *)
```

This is also an example that `iFrame` does not do forward reasoning, requiring the use of tactics such as `iSpecialize` instead. If `iFrame` could do forward reasoning, then the result might have been similar to the result of an application of `link_hyps "HP" "H"`, but it is a separate question if this is desirable behavior:

```
(* "HP" : P *)
(* "H" : P \multimap \exists x : \tau, Q x *)
(* -----* *)
(* \exists x : \tau, Q x *)
link_hyps "HP" "H" as "H"
(* "H" : \exists x : \tau, Q x *)
(* -----* *)
(* \exists x : \tau, Q x *)
```

Cleanup: In the final step of our process we clean up left over `Emps`, described in Section 4.5. This process is very similar to the process used by Krebbers et al. [2017] in IPM. In fact, the type class implementation for the `MakeSep` class is copied from it directly. The other cleanup classes that correspond to the cleanup judgments $Q \multimap^* R \overset{*}{\rightsquigarrow} [P]$, $\forall x. Q \overset{\forall}{\rightsquigarrow} [R]$ and $\exists x. Q \overset{\exists}{\rightsquigarrow} [R]$ are not present in Iris. Iris does have a different set of about ten similar classes, many of which deal with the various

modalities present in more advanced separation logics, such as the later modality \triangleright and the persistent modality \square . The reason there is no cleanup class for the wand in Iris, for example, is because framing only reduces to the right of a wand, and a resulting $P \multimap \text{Emp}$ cannot be cleaned up.

performance: Our `link` tactic currently suffers from a speed issue. Various optimizations and choices have been made to make the `iFrame` faster over time. For example, the instance for framing existential quantifiers uses an extra type class `FrameExistRequirements` to reduce the number of occurrences of the quantified goal Φ , which reduces the term size and therefore the time to type check these terms:

```
#[projections(primitive)] Class FrameExistRequirements
  (p : bool) (R : PROP) {τ} (Φ : τ → PROP) (x' : τ) (G' : PROP) := {
  frame_exist_witness : τ;
  frame_exist_resource : PROP;
  frame_exist_proof : Frame p R (Φ frame_exist_witness) frame_exist_resource;
  frame_exist_witness_eq : GatherEvarsEq frame_exist_witness x';
  frame_exist_resource_eq : TCEq frame_exist_resource G'
  }.
Global Existing Instance Build_FrameExistRequirements.
```

It also has many type classes with two variants where one of them disables backtracking for cases where backtracking is undesirable.

The proof search in our `link` tactic often does a bit of backtracking, but it is also quite slow when no backtracking is performed at all. The root cause of this is not yet known.

Connectives and other features: Obviously the `iFrame` tactic is much more mature. In this thesis we do not describe how to deal with various standard separation logic connectives such as disjunction or intuitionistic conjunction, and we do not even mention connectives from extensions for the basic separation logic, such as the persistent or later modality. Although the `iFrame` tactic does define some instances for the basic connectives, some cases such as spatial resources that can be framed in exactly one side are not handled, since that can make your goal unprovable. For example, if we have a hypothesis P and a goal $P \vee Q$, then framing will not work. Framing works well for the many modalities.

Additionally, `iFrame` tactic has various optional arguments. For example, it allows targeting a proposition to frame without providing a path but giving the term itself.

6.2.2 Diaframe

Diaframe is a proof assistant built on top of the Iris framework by Mulder et al. [2022]. It equips Iris with strong, goal-directed automation, making it competitive with non-foundational automated tools. It achieves this by structuring proof goals to enable deterministic automation. Diaframe distinguishes between unproblematic 'left-goals' and unstructured goals within separating conjunctions. When the left-most goal is unstructured, the system attempts to rewrite the current goal such that the left-most goal in a separating conjunction becomes a left-goal. Once successful, it can be discharged automatically. This allows goals to be solved systematically from left to right by repeating this process.

Rewriting these unstructured goals uses a (bi-abduction) hint system similar to subformula linking in its ability to rewrite nested subformulas and in some of the techniques employed. Specifically, the idea of Quantifying the Uninstantiated is used for these bi-abduction hints, which has the following format:

$$H * [\vec{y}; L] \models [\mathcal{E}_1 \dot{\Rightarrow} \mathcal{E}_2] \vec{x}; A * [U] \triangleq \forall \vec{y}. (H * L \vdash^{\mathcal{E}_1} \dot{\Rightarrow}^{\mathcal{E}_2} (\exists \vec{x}. A * U))$$

We see some similarities, such as the input goal A being split from an output residue U . The many differences between this hint format and the link judgments arise from the use case; to make the hint format function as desired, various quantifiers, the update modality $\dot{\Rightarrow}$, and the extra output L , which is a side condition generated by splitting it from the input hypothesis H , have been added.

6.2.3 Generalized Rewriting

Our strategy of splitting the kernel from the context described in Section 4.3 required building a context function manually using type classes. Rewriting under such a context, however, is also possible with a tactic called `setoid_rewrite` with a concept called *generalized rewriting* [Sozeau, 2009]. It is a very powerful concept that allows rewriting of under custom preorders such as \vdash from BI.

This tactic Rocq's type class system to find instances of the type class `Proper` and `subrelation` to derive how rewriting with, for example, the partial order \vdash works. This does require the user to define some of these instances, which Iris already does.

```
Class Proper {A} (R : relation A) (m : A) : Prop := { proper : R m m. }

Class subrelation {A : Type} (R R' : relation A) : Prop := {
  is subrelation :  $\Pi x y, R x y \rightarrow R' x y.$ 
}

(* Example instance for *, which demonstrates that it flips monotonicity *)
Global Instance wand_mono' : Proper (flip ( $\vdash$ )  $\Longrightarrow$  ( $\vdash$ )  $\Longrightarrow$  ( $\vdash$ )) (@bi_wand PROP).
```

Consider, for example, the following example:

```
Lemma setoid_rewrite_demo (PROP: bi) (Q R S U: PROP) (H:  $\forall P, Q * (Q -* P) \vdash P$ ):
  Q * (Q -* R * S * U) -* S * U * R.
Proof.
  setoid_rewrite H.
  (* R * S * U -* S * U * R *)
```

We think using a custom type class for contexts is appropriate in our case, however, for a few reasons. For one, this implementation was originally conceived as the basis of a real drag-and-drop based system, built on top of Rocq. For such an implementation, selecting the kernel with a *path* is a good way to direct the search, whereas `setoid_rewrite` only allows selecting the n th occurrence. Additionally, the solution proposed in Section 7.3 to potentially solve completeness seems on it face less feasible when using `setoid_rewrite`.

Chapter 7

Conclusion and Future Work

We have designed the theory of and implemented a system which allows cancelling subformula in a fragment of separation logic containing only the connectives $*$, \multimap , \forall and \exists at arbitrary depth for both hypothesis-hypothesis and hypothesis-goal links and implemented this system as our `link` tactic. We think our `link` tactic is suitable as the theoretical basis for creating an interactive drag-and-drop system like Actema, though such an implementation should probably address a problem concerning completeness we describe in Section 7.3. Finally, various extensions on linking should be interesting to explore, such as adding rewrite links described by Actema or adding rules for the various extension of Separation logic, with perhaps the ultimate goal of supporting the entire Iris logic.

Next, in Sections 7.1 to 7.3, we discuss future work to address some of the limitations of the current theory and implementation and how to solve these problems. We also mention some possible extensions in Section 7.4 and some considerations concerning a graphical user interface Section 7.5.

7.1 Scope

We currently only describe rules for a limited subset of BI. Propositions that contain the connectives \wedge , \vee or \rightarrow are not supported. Of these connectives, we consider \vee to be the most interesting, mainly considering the limited scope in which the intuitionistic \wedge and \rightarrow are used in separation logic.

Consider the left backward rules for disjunction in intuitionistic logic, $\text{LB}\vee\text{L}$ from Mulder and Krebbers [2024], for example. In these rules the \blacktriangleright replaces a single occurrence of \rightarrow , similar to how \multimap replaces a single occurrence of \multimap :

$$\text{LB}\vee\text{L} \quad \frac{[P] \models Q_{\text{L}} \blacktriangleright R}{[P \wedge (Q_{\text{R}} \rightarrow R)] \models Q_{\text{L}} \vee Q_{\text{R}} \blacktriangleright R}$$

Translating this rule directly to separation logic has two options. We have to replace the implications with wands, but we can consider whether or not to replace the conjunction with a separating conjunction or not. If we do not, the rule is sound, but requires at least some support for standard conjunctions as well. We are unsure if adding support only for conjunctions which are generated by this rule would be easier than more thorough support for conjunction or not. Otherwise, if we do replace the conjunction with a separating conjunction, the rule is not sound in a linear (non-affine) separation logic. This is because the Q_{L} case in the conclusion does not consume the resource $(Q_{\text{R}} \multimap R)$, and the Q_{R} case in the conclusion does not consume the P resource. It is also not immediately clear

how to adapt the rule to resolve this problem by changing just the shape of the output, which is the only part we are able to change in a straightforward implementation. Since the disjunction is before an arrow, there is also no similar implementation for `iFrame` to take inspiration from.

7.2 Performance

The implementation currently is on the slow side. For example, executing line 9 from Figure 3.2 takes about 2 seconds. Based on some experimentation, this performance problem does not seem to result from an exponential blowup. The exact cause of this slowdown is not yet known, however.

7.3 Completeness

The system of proving by linking for the fragment of BI that only contains `*`, `-*` and quantifiers is currently not complete. Consider, for example, the proposition

$$\forall x. \exists y. F x \multimap F y$$

When we want to link the terms $F x$ and $F y$, we apply the rules `SPLIT \forall` and `SPLIT \exists` during the splitting of the context step. This second rule, however, *introduces* a fresh quantifier y . This is a problem in this case, because the y should have been substituted with x . We do however, desire to maintain the capability of introducing the quantifier for existential quantification. For example, if we have a proposition $\exists x. F x \multimap F x$, we would like to be able to simplify this to $\exists x. F x \multimap F x$, even if we do not have access to a quantifier.

This problem should seem familiar, as it is a very similar problem solved by Quantifying the Uninstantiated during linking. Although we have made some attempts to do this, the double interaction with telescopes have eluded these attempts thus far. For example, the type of the function $f : TT \rightarrow \tau$ from the implementation of `LINK-LB \forall -QU` should probably change to account for the changing telescope and become dependent: $f' : \forall x : \tau. \text{Make}TT x \xrightarrow{t} \tau$, which also requires a change to the resolution of this function.

7.4 Extensions

Apart from adding the basic connectives, separation logic has been extended with many more connectives and modalities, many of which are present in the logic of Iris, such as the \triangleright modality for step-indexing and the \square modality for reusable propositions. Additionally, we have ignored the presence of the persistent context. All of these features of the logic of Iris and extensions would be good extensions for our linking system as well.

Additionally, Actema defines a different type of link, where values are rewritten using equalities. Another possible extension is to add this type of link to our system. Adding this to our system might entail adding a single terminal inference rule, but some challenges will have to be solved such as the persistence of equality. Additionally, once such a terminal rule has been found it would be interesting to explore its effect, applications, user-friendliness and explore whether it can be extended to rewriting partial orders, similar to generalized rewriting [Sozeau, 2009].

7.5 Interface

Creating a graphical user interface to allow drag-and-drop interactions based on our system is a challenge we do not tackle in this paper. Various solution directions are possible. One possible solution is to make a completely separate application that interacts with the Rocq engine. This implementation is most similar to the original implementation of Proof by Pointing for Rocq, CtCoq [Bertot et al., 1994] and its successor Pcoq [Amerkad et al., 2002]. It could even be made into a web-based application if compiled with something like JsCoq [Arias et al., 2016] or by hosting the engine on a server. Alternatively, one could attempt to build a extension in VsCode, which could interact with VsRocq’s language server similar to the VsRocq extension [VsRocq Development Team, 2025]. Lastly, a completely stand-alone application could be made which did not rely on Rocq at all, but implements a specialized version of type class search to generate new goals. This implementation is the direction chosen by both ProfInt and Actema, although only former is capable of exporting proofs.

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